

> DESIRE6G <

D3.1: Initial report on the intelligent and secure management, orchestration, and control platform

HEU 6G SNS JU Project

Grant No. 101096466

Co-funded by
the European Union

Document properties

Document number	D3.1
Document title	Initial report on the intelligent and secure management, orchestration, and control platform
Work Package	3
Editors	Vincent Lefebvre (TSS)
Authors	Merve Saimler, Sultan Ertas (EBY), Cyril Hsu, Chrysa Papagianni (UVA), Luis Velasco, Marc Ruiz, Jaume Comellas, Sima Barzegar (UPC), Milan Groshev, Adam Zahir Rodriguez (UC3M), Vincent Lefebvre (TSS), Alessandro Pacini, Luca Valcarengi, Andrea Sgambelluri (SSSA), Anastassios Nanos, George Ntoutsos, Christos Panagiotou (NUBIS), Charbel Bou Chaaya and Chathuranga Weeraddana (UOU), Alejandro Muñiz Da Costa (TID)
Internal reviewers	Anastassios Nanos (NUBIS), Chrysa Papagianni (UVA)
External reviewers	Gergely Pongracz (ERI-HU), Roberto Gonzalez (NEC)
Dissemination level	PU (Public)
Status of the document	Final
Version	1.3
File name	DESIRE6G_D3_1_Initial_report_intelligent_secure_management_orchestration_control_platform_V1.3
Contractual delivery date	November 30, 2023
Delivery date	November 30, 2023

Document history

Revision	Date	Issued by	Description
V0.1	15/09/2023	TSS/NUBIS	Draft ToC/Sections
V0.2	03-11/2023	TSS/NUBIS	Semi Final
V1	23/11/2023	TSS/NUBIS	Pre-Final version (for external reviewers)
V1.1	28/11/2023	TSS/NUBIS	Submitted Final version
V1.2 - V1.3	30/11/23	Teresa Calafat	Format fixed

Abstract

This document summarizes the first 11 months of work on WP3, presenting the initial architecture of the DESIRE6G Service and Management Orchestrator, along with its components and the technologies used to achieve flexible and intelligent service instantiation and management on a 6G network.

Keywords

SMO, MAS, Intent-based translation, DLT federation, Security, Policy

Disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101096466.

DESIRE6G is supported by the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking.

This report reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	11
2. High level architecture	13
3. E2E Service Management and Orchestration	15
3.1. E2E SMO overview	15
3.1.1. OSM.....	16
3.1.2. ONAP	17
3.1.3. DESIRE6G SMO	17
3.2. Intent-based Network Management.....	22
3.2.1. Introduction.....	22
3.2.2. Service Creation Steps	23
3.3. Intent-based Management of Network Slicing	27
3.3.1. Working Mechanism of SLA-intent Translation.....	27
3.3.2. Intent-based management.....	28
3.3.3. Intent-based management for Transport domain.....	28
3.4. Hybrid container runtime.....	29
3.4.1. Efficient Sandboxing of Containers on Edge Nodes.....	30
3.4.2. Sandboxed Containers	33
3.4.3. Unikernels as Containers	36
3.4.4. bima: unikernel container images.....	36
3.4.5. urunc: a unikernel container runtime	38
3.5. Application-Layer Traffic Optimization	39
3.6. DLT federation	42
3.6.1. Service federation procedures.....	43

3.6.2. Federation challenges.....	44
3.6.3. Federation using DLT (blockchain + smart contract).....	46
3.6.4. DLT-based federation in SMO.....	48
4. Multi-Agent System.....	51
4.1. MAS architecture.....	52
4.2. Machine Learning Function Orchestrator.....	54
4.3. MAS SECURITY.....	57
4.3.1. Agent exposure and security needs.....	57
4.3.2. Agent security by-design by SECaaS.....	58
4.3.3. Inter-agent trust building.....	61
4.3.4. DLT relevance for MAS security:.....	62
4.3.5. Federation of service for mutual remote attestation.....	63
4.3.6. DLT-backed Mutual Remote Attestation sequencing.....	65
4.3.7. Secure Execution Monitoring.....	66
4.4. Near Real-Time Secure MAS Operation.....	67
4.5. MAS Deployment.....	68
5. Robust, sustainable and privacy preserving AI in DESIRE6G.....	70
5.1. Distributed Edge Intelligence.....	70
5.2. Forecasting Element to support 6G operations.....	75
5.3. Confidentiality preserving data exchange with third party xApp.....	76
5.4. ML-based assisted SLA Decomposition.....	78
5.5. Elastic Scaling.....	81
6. Conclusion.....	84
7. References.....	85

List of Figures

FIGURE 1 HIGH LEVEL ARCHITECTURE13

FIGURE 2 DESIRE6G DRAFT SMO ARCHITECTURE18

FIGURE 3 SERVICE INSTANTIATION WORKFLOW (SMO).....21

FIGURE 4. SERVICE CREATION (DESIGN, ORCHESTRATION AND RUN TIME)23

FIGURE 5. EXAMPLE OF INTENT-DRIVEN OPERATION FOR TRANSPORT DOMAINS.....29

FIGURE 6. HIGH-LEVEL OVERVIEW OF GENERIC CONTAINER SPAWNING IN A K8S ENVIRONMENT30

FIGURE 7. CONTAINER SANDBOXING32

FIGURE 8. PACKING A UNIKERNEL AS AN OCI-COMPATIBLE CONTAINER IMAGE.....36

FIGURE 9. CONTAINER FILE SAMPLE38

FIGURE 10. RUNNING AN UNPACKED CONTAINER IMAGE AS A UNIKERNEL39

FIGURE 11. BASIC ALTO ARCHITECTURE (FROM RFC7285).....40

FIGURE 12. NETWORKMAP AND COSTMAP EXAMPLES41

FIGURE 13. ALTO SERVER INTERACTION WITH MLFO MODULE.42

FIGURE 14. DLT FEDERATION FOR THE SMO.....49

FIGURE 15 WORKFLOW DIAGRAM FOR DLT SERVICE FEDERATION PROCESS50

FIGURE 16. ARCHITECTURE OF THE MAS AGENTS.....53

FIGURE 17. MAS FOR SERVICE MANAGEMENT AND RELATED INTERFACES.....54

FIGURE 18. AI/ML PIPELINE TEMPLATE (A), DEPLOYMENT (B) AND RECONFIGURATION (C).55

FIGURE 19. GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF AGENT SECURITY59

FIGURE 20. AGENT REWRITING SEQUENCING66

FIGURE 21. AGENT MUTUAL ATTESTATION SEQUENCING.....66

FIGURE 22. ML PIPELINE DEPLOYMENT WORKFLOW68

FIGURE 23. FEDERATED SETTING FOR EDGE COMMUNICATION/COMPUTING70

FIGURE 24. DEPLOYING INTELLIGENCE AT RIS72

FIGURE 25 CONVERGENCE OF ALGORITHMS73

FIGURE 26. EDGE COMMUNICATION/COMPUTING FOR INTELLIGENCE.....73

FIGURE 27. COMPUTATION/COMMUNICATION ENERGY COSTS AND CORRESPONDING CARBON
FOOTPRINTS FOR THE PHISHING DATASET FOR A TARGET OPTIMALITY GAP 10^{-5} 74

FIGURE 28. FE AND RADIO SEGMENT.....76

FIGURE 29 CONFIDENTIALITY PRESERVATION SOLUTION77

FIGURE 31. SLA DECOMPOSITION79

FIGURE 32 RISK MODEL EVALUATION.....80

FIGURE 33 AVG. E2E ACCEPTANCE PROBABILITY.....80

FIGURE 33. V2N IN D6G.....82

FIGURE 34. AVERAGED NUMBER OF CPUS.....83

FIGURE 35. AVERAGED REWARD83

List of Tables

Table 1. Process Execution Environment.....	34
Table 2. Federation Challenges.....	46
Table 3. Security Enforcement Of Current SECaaS.....	60
Table 4. Security Enforcement From SECaaS Developments.....	61

List of Acronyms

AD	Administrative Domain
ALTO	Application Traffic Layout Optimization
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CNF	Container Network Function
CLI	Command Line Interface
CRI	Container Runtime Interface
CRI-IO	A CRI compatible with OCI, implementing the Kubelet Container Runtime
C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle to Everything
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DPU	Data Processing Unit
FaaS	Function as a Service
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
MAS	Multi-Agent System
IBM	Intent-Based Management
IBN	Intent-Based Network
I/O	Input/Output
IML	Infrastructure Management Layer
LAN	Local Area Network
ML	Machine Learning
MLFO	Machine Learning Function Orchestrator
NBI	Northbound Interface
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVO	Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator
QoS	Quality of Service
rApp	Software Application designed to run on the Non-Real Time RAN Intelligent Control
RAN	Radio Access to Network
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
RIC	Ran Intelligent Controller

RRU	Remote Radio Unit
UE	User Equipment
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLO	Service Level Objective
ttRPC	A container sub-project (for low level simple transfer protocol)
SDN	Software Defined Network
SMO	Service Management and Orchestration
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
VIM	Virtualized Infrastructure Manager
VM	Virtual Machine
VNF	Virtual Network Function
xAPP	Software Application for near-real time RIC automation and management

Executive Summary

In this document we capture our initial exploration on intelligent and secure management, orchestration and control. The document describes the work done during the first 11 months in WP3 and is focused on the three major contributions of WP3 to the DESIRE6G implementation: (a) E2E service management and orchestration, (b) the Multi-agent System and (c) on Robust, Sustainable and Privacy-preserving AI/ML.

Key contributions

The first section describes our initial considerations on the Service Management and Orchestration layer (SMO) acting as the core service management and orchestration entity. The key contributions are outlined below:

- We decouple the fine-grained service orchestration placement from the SMO, bringing this functionality to the DESIRE6G sites (closer to where the service is being instantiated). This is achieved through the delegation of traditional SMO functionality to a thin layer on top of the VIM, leaving the SMO out of the critical path, handling more high-level orchestration decisions.
- We introduce efficient federation functionality to the SMO, leveraging DLT-based approaches.
- We optimize Intent-based service management through an efficient translation mechanism.
- We introduce a secure Multi-Agent System (MAS) to minimize response time. Control algorithms are executed as close as possible to the data sources, significantly reducing control loop latencies for service adaptation.
- We enable the use of AI/ML techniques, to address demanding 6G requirements. We explore how the edge resources are effectively used and we employ ML-based approaches to address problems on orchestration and lifecycle management of network services.

1. Introduction

During the first 11 months of the project, the involved partners in Work Package 3 have been working on the preliminary design of the AI-enabled service management and orchestration layer and the secure multi-agent approach of the DESIRE6G architecture. Working closely with the partners involved in WP2 which defines the requirements and the overall architecture, we have identified focus points that need elaborate analysis.

A major point of discussion is the design of the **Service and Management Orchestrator** (SMO) layer (T3.1). The involved partners have been iterating over various designs, open-source and commercially available and explore the trade-offs of each solution (Section 3). Another valuable of the work relates to the definition of a custom container runtime, devised to bring security and namely isolation without impeding execution performances. The solution also enables to differentiate the way services and applications are instantiated based on descriptors defined in the SMO, a central cross-domain entity able to instantiate service, network functions and agents over the complete end-to-end service. Moreover, partners have been exploring various aspects of DLT, taking advantage of its security and traceability features, as well as its flexible and incremental use by smart contracts. To this end, a DLT network has been employed for Service Federation, enabling dynamic and secure interactions between different administrative domains at the orchestration level in the SMO.

In addition to this, WP3 effort has been spent on the design of the **secure Multi-Agent System** (MAS) (T3.2). The MAS-based approach is being defined both in high-level terms (its relation to the SMO layers), as well as in low-level terms (which operations a component performs). An on-going analysis is being conducted to determine the granularity of responsibilities the MAS has with respect to the SMO and the lower levels of the software stack. At the same time, WP3 work has focused on the security aspects of the system (T3.2), with particular emphasis in securing the MAS and the individual workloads that will be deployed in DESIRE6G (e.g., xApps, NFs, application workloads). To that end, DLT and smart contracts has been studied for two different usages; (i) secure distribution of VxLAN keys to establish inter-agent communication and (ii) establishing a novel agent mutual attestation mechanism, based on a software-

based chain of trust and in which agents are able to check the authenticity of other agents which whom they come into play.

In the era of **pervasive AI**, our work has included initial considerations and results on AI/ML algorithms, to be used at different levels of the DESIRE6G architecture, e.g., SMO, MAS, and edge. Preliminary investigations within DESIRE6G explore integrating intelligence across various tiers of its architecture to meet the stringent demands of 6G requirements. This includes employing AI/ML algorithms in MAS for service automation, supported by a ML Function Orchestrator (MLFO). At the edge, ML algorithms operate in a federated setting, ensuring data privacy, and investigations focus on their effectiveness with both homogeneous and heterogeneous datasets to strengthen algorithm robustness. Research also delves into deploying novel forecasting components at edge nodes using real-time telemetry data, aiding for instance DESIRE6G system service assurances, among others. Moreover, initial studies are looking into using ML-based approaches to address network service orchestration and lifecycle management at the SMO level. The adoption of forecasting techniques will be studied and developed to assist the automatic operations at the RAN, consuming the near real time telemetry data collected from the network to produce forecasting metrics to assist in slice control. Moreover, innovative software-implemented homomorphic confidentiality preserving solutions in the radio segment will be investigated addressing the communication with third party rApps. Finally, we are looking into approaches pertaining to ML-assisted service lifecycle management. We investigate how at the SMO level, an E2E SLA associated to a service, may be decomposed to partial SLAs assigned to the different network segments (RAN/edge, transport, core). We assume that the SMO has limited knowledge on admission control for previous requests and captures this knowledge employing Neural Network-based risk models. Furthermore, we investigate a Deep Reinforcement learning approach to support service elasticity in the context of a Cellular Vehicular-to-Network (C-V2N) service, adhering to the MAS approach in DESIRE6G.

2. High level architecture

FIGURE 1 HIGH LEVEL ARCHITECTURE

Note: this section is based on Deliverable 2.1: Definition of Use Cases, Service Requirements and KPIs/KVIs [43]. It is included here to facilitate understanding of the terms and concepts discussed in this document.

Figure 1 high level architecture shows DESIRE6G's high-level architecture, replicated in each 6G processing sites including RAN, core network, edge and User Equipment (UE). The network consists of topologically separated DESIRE6G sites, including local HW and compute resources running NFs necessary for the execution of the network services and application functions (AFs) required by the (application-specific) services. Each DESIRE6G site has almost identical setup with slight differences based on necessity, e.g., the sites running Radio Access Network (RAN) functionality are equipped with sufficient hardware entities and/or non-programmable (static) functions, all of which are still considered NFs by the system. Also note that the User Equipment (UE) might also be able to run a stripped-down version of the DESIRE6G stack using its own hardware and software stacks. This is a big difference compared to existing UE approaches and it makes E2E service control possible. Of course, legacy UEs can still use the system as today attaching to some "edge-to-edge" service, e.g., normal Internet access. Between the DESIRE6G sites there can be non-programmable elements. These can be controlled by Software-Defined Networking Controller(s) (SDN-C) or by traditional routing protocols. The minimum

requirement is that the DESIRE6G infrastructure must understand the reachability of the other sites from each given site (e.g., IP addresses of the other site's gateway).

The architecture's core functional blocks are Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) layer, the Multi-Agent System (MAS) and Programmable Data Plane (PDP), all empowered by AI.

- Service Management and Orchestration (SMO): Similar to existing specifications (i.e., NFV orchestrator for ETSI MANO), the SMO is responsible for end-to-end service life-cycle management, including service provisioning and deployment, network slice management and network optimizations. It contains several modules responsible for these different tasks and it is the main interface towards the external world. In addition, the SMO is also responsible for the management and orchestration of the Open RAN components, including Open Central Unit (O-CU), Open Distributed Unit (O-DU) functions, and near-real-time radio intelligent controller (Near RT-RIC)
- Multi-Agent-based network intelligence System (MAS) and telemetry: MAS implements distributed network intelligence closer to the physical infrastructure, as it is responsible for receiving service-specific monitoring information and fine-tuning the network and compute resources. It configures and uses a pervasive telemetry system to receive service specific KPIs, e.g., by monitoring end-to-end latency for latency-sensitive or latency-critical services.
- Programmable Data Plane (PDP) layer including the Infrastructure Management Layer (IML) and the HW/SW specific implementations of the NFs: The E2E Programmable Data Plane is employing NFs to carry out the logic of the selected service. NFs contain a Control Plane component (NF-CP) and the packet processing Data Plane logic (NF-DP). Note that at this level the main role of NF-CP is to configure and update the objects (e.g., tables, registers, etc.) in the corresponding NF-DP. These are separated by the IML responsible for transparent scaling, acceleration, and deployment, i.e., it is the bridge between the logical and the physical network function. IML hides the implementation and deployment details of NF-DP from NF-CP by providing a simple unified view of the data plane. For example, even if NF-DP is vertically or horizontally disaggregated into multiple data plane programs running on different HW/SW targets, IML ensures that NF-CP only sees a single NF-DP instance and IML handles the complexity of managing the disaggregated packet processing components.

3. E2E Service Management and Orchestration

3.1. E2E SMO overview

Network functions and applications, in the context of telecom use-cases and operators require sophisticated orchestration to ensure optimal performance, reliability, and scalability. Service and management and orchestration options for telecom workloads typically involve the use of advanced software-defined networking (SDN) and network functions virtualization (NFV) technologies. On the one hand, SDN enables network operators to programmatically control network traffic flows, which can be particularly useful for managing radio access networks (RANs) and their associated base stations. Machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI) algorithm are applied in RAN orchestration to optimize network performance, automate routine tasks, and reduce costs. On the other hand, NFV allows telecom workloads to be virtualized and run on commodity hardware, enabling operators to deploy network functions and applications more quickly and cost-effectively. Management and orchestration of virtualized telecom workloads involve automated processes, including deployment, scaling, and healing. In the context of DESIRE6G, we are particularly interested in the modularity of the orchestration platform, as our individual research focus spans diverse fields and it would be great if we could integrate all into a single SMO platform, to showcase the project's merits.

There are several SMO frameworks available, including:

- **Open-Source Orchestration Frameworks:** These frameworks provide an open-source solution for managing telecom workloads, including service and network function orchestration. Examples of such frameworks include Open Source MANO (OSM)¹ from ETSI and Open Network Automation Platform (ONAP)² from the Linux Foundation.

¹ <https://osm.etsi.org/>

²² <https://www.onap.org/>

- **Commercial Orchestration Platforms:** Commercial orchestration platforms provide a complete solution for managing telecom workloads. These platforms typically provide a range of features and tools, such as automated service delivery, resource optimization, and network analytics. Examples of commercial orchestration platforms include Nokia's Network Services Platform (NSP)³ and Ericsson's Cloud Manager⁴.

In the context of DESIRE6G, we are particularly interested in the modularity of (existing) orchestration platforms, to facilitate the integration of the DESIRE6G SMO innovations into a single platform and showcase the project's merits.

3.1.1. OSM

OSM (Open Source MANO) is an open-source orchestration framework that provides a comprehensive solution for managing telecom workloads, including service and network function orchestration. It is a project hosted by ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) and has been designed to support the end-to-end orchestration of virtualized network functions (VNFs) and services.

OSM enables operators to deploy and manage network services in a multi-vendor, multi-technology, and multi-domain environment. It provides a modular architecture that allows the integration of different network technologies and functions, including RAN, core networks, and applications. OSM also provides a rich set of features for service onboarding, instantiation, and lifecycle management, as well as service assurance and analytics.

³ <https://www.nokia.com/networks/ip-networks/network-services-platform/>

⁴ <https://www.ericsson.com/en/portfolio/networks/ericsson-cloud-ran/cloud-ran-infrastructure/cloud-infrastructure>

OSM is gaining popularity among telecom operators and vendors as it offers a flexible and scalable platform for deploying and managing telecom workloads. It has a growing community of contributors and supporters and is being adopted by several telecom operators and vendors worldwide.

3.1.2. ONAP

ONAP (Open Network Automation Platform) is an open-source platform that provides end-to-end automation and orchestration of network services. It is designed to automate the entire lifecycle of network services, including design, creation, monitoring, and management. ONAP provides a modular architecture that supports a wide range of use cases, including mobile, fixed, and cloud networks. The following are the key components of the ONAP architecture:

- **Design Time:** This component includes tools for designing and modeling network services and functions. The design time component allows network operators to create network service blueprints that can be used to automate the deployment and management of network services.
- **Controller Platform:** This component includes the core orchestration engine that manages the lifecycle of network services. The controller platform is responsible for service creation, deployment, scaling, and termination.
- **Policy Framework:** This component includes a policy engine that enables network operators to define and enforce policies for network services. The policy framework provides a mechanism for automating complex network decisions and actions.
- **Analytics Framework:** This component includes tools for collecting, processing, and analyzing network data. The analytics framework enables network operators to monitor and optimize network services based on real-time data and insights.
- **Virtual Function (VF) Manager:** This component includes tools for managing and orchestrating virtual network functions (VNFs). The VF manager enables network operators to deploy, scale, and manage VNFs on virtualized infrastructure.

3.1.3. DESIRE6G SMO

To examine the options available, we initiated work on T3.1 by deploying an OSM testbed. Although OSM provides the functionality the DESIRE6G SMO needs, it also complicates the process and adds

significant overhead. Since most of the direct Network Function management operations are handled in the IML, in DESIRE6G we simplified the design of the SMO to the absolute minimum functionality, offered by microservices that are described hereafter.

FIGURE 2 DESIRE6G DRAFT SMO ARCHITECTURE

Figure 2 depicts the initial DESIRE6G SMO architecture broken down to the respective microservices (IBM, Service Catalogue, Service Orchestrator, Policy framework, Topology, Non-RT RIC, MLFO, Monitoring and Data lake), as defined by the requirements of the use-cases analysed in WP2, as well as the definition of the DESIRE6G overall framework. Specifically, the DESIRE6G SMO is divided into two main components:

Design time Templates & Service Catalogue: this is where the templates for the network services, applications, and, in general, all pre-defined components of a service are stored and created. This component uses already existing templates as well as intent-translated service definitions.

Runtime components: this is where the basic functionalities of the SMO are implemented. Specifically, (a) the service instantiation and life-cycle management of services and applications (Service Orchestrator, Topology, Non-RT RIC) (b) the initial instantiation and life-cycle management of the MAS (MLFO); (c) the intelligence regarding the initial placement and allocation of resources for the instantiated services (Policy Framework); (d) the monitoring and telemetry management framework (Monitoring, Data lake).

The Design-time components, along with Intent-based Management (IBM) are discussed in detail in Subsection 3.2. A brief description of all components is shown below:

Service Design & Service Catalogue: Service design plays a central role in coordinating Service Lifecycle Management (LCM) alongside blueprint management during the creation of a service or network slice. Service descriptions are stored in the catalogue. This is a rather static subsystem: service introduction is done with setting the service graphs for the required service along with other parameters, such as QoS. The catalogue entries (service descriptions) can be defined manually but can also be set via an intent-based service definition framework. Backstage⁵ is an open-source platform designed to manage the end-to-end development and deployment of microservices-based applications. It provides a centralized catalog of services and components, which can be used to discover, manage, and reuse services across different teams and projects. In the context of DESIRE6G, Backstage can be used as a service catalog software service to store and manage the descriptors of network functions and services that are available for deployment on the target infrastructure. The catalog includes information about the VNF packages, service descriptors, and other metadata that are required for service deployment and management, such as annotated Service Graphs, application bundles etc.

Service Orchestrator: The Service orchestrator (and high-level network function orchestrator - NFVO) is the key entity at service deployment. The orchestrator has full understanding of the operator's DESIRE6G sites including site resources and inter-site connections. It instructs the IML that plays the

⁵ <https://backstage.io/>

role of the VNF Manager in the ETSI MANO terminology, while also wrapping VIM functionality, to deploy NF-sub-graphs to selected sites. It is also involved in full or partial service re-deployments when requested by the underlying MAS.

Topology component: The Topology component maps the DESIRE6G network, both in terms of network topology, as well as in terms of high-level compute capabilities: the network topology, along with annotations from the various network links and weights is captured from the ALTO component (discussed in Section 3.5); the compute capabilities is captured from the IML, mapping available CPU cores/hardware acceleration and switch infrastructure that each sites provides.

Non-Real-time RIC: The Non Real-time RIC component supports non-real-time radio resource management, higher layer procedure optimization, policy optimization in RAN, and provides guidance, parameters, policies and AI/ML models to support the operation of near-RealTime RIC functions in the RAN to achieve higher-level non-real-time objectives.

MLFO: the machine learning function Orchestrator that manages and monitors all the elements and resources that build an AI pipeline.

Policy: The policy framework adds intelligence to service orchestration and lifecycle management. Section 5 elaborates on the ML-based approach used to achieve this, focusing on SLA decomposition (SLA).

Monitoring & Data lake: The Monitoring service including a cloud data lake, that is the repository where data (processed telemetry information, events etc.) is stored. The Data lake is essentially a repository to store all telemetry data and binary artifacts. Specifically, it features a wrapper service that supports multiple protocols, each one of which is tailored to the specific use-case: for telemetry, we expose a timeseries DB interface, for network function artifacts, we expose a container registry interface, whereas for general storage we expose an object-store interface (s3). Service graphs, point to the data lake for network function- and application-level binary artifacts.

Selected individual components that comprise the SMO, as well as the technologies used to encompass the DESIRE6G concept are elaborated in the sections that follow. The Infrastructure Management Layer (IML), defined in WP2 and implemented in WP4 is an enhanced VIM/NF API, that manages infrastructure and services instantiation, as well as data-plane acceleration functionality. The SMO interacts directly

with both the IML and VIM/NF API (if needed). As part of service deployment (mainly relevant to IML component), we describe the low-level characteristics of the services deployed by the service descriptors to the DESIRE6G sites (Section 3.4). To federate multiple instances of the D6G SMO, DLT federation techniques are exposed in section 3.6. The MLFO component instantiates and manages the life cycle of the MAS. Specifically, it interacts with the Service Orchestrator to spawn MAS agents on the infrastructure, alongside NFs.

FIGURE 3 SERVICE INSTANTIATION WORKFLOW (SMO)

Figure 3 visualizes the service instantiation steps on behalf of a tenant, until the actual deployment on Edge and Core DESIRE6G sites. This workflow involves all the available components of the SMO, ranging from the Service site catalogue (where the initial service graphs are stored), up to the instantiation trigger on the IML (the component that deploys the service at the sites).

- Step 1: A request is issued to the Service Orchestrator (SO).
- Step 2: The SO gets the service graph and the service parameters from the Service Catalogue (SC).
- Step 3: In case of a non-existent service graph, an error is returned to the Tenant.
- Step 4: The Topology Database (TB) is populated by querying the individual sites (this could be cached, or re-triggered for updates).

- Step 5: The SO requests the site topology from the TB.
- Step 6: The SO requests the service sub-graphs from the Policy Framework component (PC) and the Intent Component (IC).
- Step 7: If needed, the SO configures the SDN controller (SDNC).
- Step 8: The SO issues requests to the IML(s) of each site where the service will be instantiated.
- Steps 9-10: If the service is deployed successfully, the IML(s) issue successful completion responses to the SO.
- Step 11: The SO triggers the deployment of the MAS agents to the sites where the service has been instantiated.
- Step 12: The SO sends a successful response to the Tenant that requested the deployment.

3.2. Intent-based Network Management

3.2.1. Introduction

In the realm of network architecture, the concept of an intent-based network (IBN) harnesses the principles of intent-based management, empowering users to articulate high-level intentions and desired outcomes for the network. This architecture automatically translates and implements these intentions into tangible configurations and actions, reflecting a user-centric and dynamic approach to network management. As we delve into the dynamic landscape of 5G and 6G networks, the significance of intent-based management transcends its foundational role in network slicing intricacies. Its impact on resource optimization and user experience within network slices is palpable, yet its reach extends further, addressing broader challenges in the evolving network paradigms. Positioned as a cornerstone for network evolution, intent-based management becomes instrumental in providing abstraction and automation, facilitating efficient resource allocation, optimizing network performance, and ensuring the desired service quality. This transformative approach lays the groundwork for diverse and innovative use cases across different sectors.

Within the intricate lifecycle of network slices, intent-based management emerges as a comprehensive and transformative force, ensuring not only the efficiency of resource utilization but also strict adherence to service-level agreements (SLAs). The streamlined methodology simplifies complex

processes involved in creating, modifying, and terminating network slices, leveraging automation and a unified framework. This role extends into SLA management, where continuous monitoring, real-time data analysis, and adaptive actions uphold desired service levels, fostering consistency and reliability. Beyond operational efficiency, intent-based management plays a pivotal role in automating complex network operations, eliminating manual processes, and dynamically allocating resources based on user-expressed intents. This automation, accompanied by proactive monitoring and self-healing capabilities, enhances operational efficiency, minimizing downtime. Furthermore, it offers granular control over network resources, optimizing Quality of Service (QoS) and user experience by aligning network behaviour with specific user expectations. The ability to capture user intents and dynamically meet specific requirements positions intent-based management as a transformative force in the evolution of 5G and 6G networks, driving innovation across diverse sectors and paving the way for networks that seamlessly adapt to user intents.

3.2.2. Service Creation Steps

FIGURE 4. SERVICE CREATION (DESIGN, ORCHESTRATION AND RUN TIME)

The development and provisioning of network services in contemporary telecommunications represent an intricate and multifaceted process that integrates a multitude of components and strategies. The

outset of this procedure involves the critical phase of service management as shown in Figure 4. The Service orchestrator is the pivotal component tasked with orchestrating the entire service creation process. The following processes are executed upon receipt of a new service request:

1. The journey commences when a Service Level Agreement (SLA), a foundational document outlining the agreement's terms and conditions, is transmitted to Service Management via Northbound Interfaces (NBIs). These interfaces include various communication protocols, such as NETCONF⁶ and YANG⁷, Open APIs, and RESTful APIs. The SLA is the crux of this initial interaction and encapsulates essential sections that comprise detailed service descriptions, measurable performance objectives, delineation of responsibilities for all involved parties, availability and support specifics, escalation procedures, monitoring and reporting processes, as well as provisions for service credits or penalties. The centrality of the SLA within the service creation process is fundamental, as it sets the stage for all subsequent operations. In particular, it delineates the expectations and requirements of the telecommunication service, thereby serving as the blueprint upon which the service will be built.
2. Following the submission of the SLA, the process advances with the translation of pertinent SLA components into intent representation. This translation process, referred to as SLA-to-Intent translation, involves the conversion of SLA content into formats like Resource Description Framework (RDF)⁸ and Unified Modelling Language (UML)⁹. The intent representation, as thus derived, forms the basis for the high-level intent for the network.
3. Upon the establishment of this high-level intent, Service Management initiates a pivotal step in the service creation process by verifying the existence of the requested service within the service catalogue.

⁶ <https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Netconf>

⁷ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc6020>

⁸ https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Resource_Description_Framework

⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unified_Modeling_Language

- a) If the desired service is indeed catalogued, the service catalogue provides current service information. Subsequently, Service Management leverages this data to facilitate the integration of the new service with the existing one. The service catalogue, in this context, performs the role of establishing the necessary connections within its own data store and initiates runtime functions to reconfigure the existing service definition based on the new service mapping. This reconfiguration encompasses alterations to resource definitions, the introduction of new service definitions for associated network functions, policy configurations, and considerations for utilization constraints.
- b) However, if the requested service is not found in the service catalogue, the catalogue communicates this information to Service Management, signifying the need to embark on creating a new service from the ground up.
 - i. Service Design is then activated to craft a new service blueprint in response to this requirement.
 - ii. Intent decomposition is the ensuing phase in the service creation process. In this stage, the service is dissected into its constituent network functions, or virtualized network functions (VNFs). This critical process unravels the interdependencies that underpin the functions and necessitates the formulation of a Service Function Chain or service graph that specifies the order in which these functions will be executed. Importantly, the existing service information is sourced from the service catalogue to facilitate this decomposition. During this period, intent decomposition transpires, resulting in the creation of sub-intents. These sub-intents break down the high-level intent into more granular elements, aligning them with the service graph and decomposition. This also involves the specification of interfaces for each sub-intent to facilitate seamless communication.
 - iii. Once service/intent decomposition is complete, the next imperative step is to define the rules and regulations governing the network functions and the service as a whole. The establishment of a policy framework is pivotal in this context. This framework is instrumental in creating service-related policies designed to uphold the service's Service Level Objectives (SLOs). The policy framework encompasses a spectrum of

policies, including security policies, traffic management policies, and resource allocation policies, which must harmonize with the service's overarching objectives and requirements.

- iv. With the aid of the service decomposition and policy framework, a service graph is crafted to visually depict the flow of traffic through network functions. To realize this, the service graph draws upon the topology database, which is tasked with providing information regarding the physical and virtual network infrastructure. This database comprehensively records data related to network devices, including their spatial distribution, capacities, and interconnections. The accuracy and timeliness of data within the topology database are crucial to ensuring that it faithfully reflects changes in the network infrastructure.
- v. Following these preliminary and foundational stages, Service Management proceeds to the critical phase of testing and validating the sub-intents that have been meticulously constructed. This entails a rigorous assessment and testing of the sub-intents. Subsequently, Service Management shares the sub-intents and service graphs with sub-domain management structures to expedite the establishment of configurations.
- vi. The next step of the service creation process involves the transmission of information from Service Management to Service Design, confirming the successful creation of the service.
- vii. Service Design, in turn, calls upon the catalogue to comprehensively document the newly minted service. This documentation encompasses the utilization of the service graph, an elucidation of the service's specifications, and the provision of all requisite information. The catalogue, thus, assumes a pivotal role in encapsulating the blueprint of the newly created service. In conclusion, the creation of network services in modern telecommunications is an intricate and interwoven process that spans multiple steps and relies on diverse components. The Service Level Agreement (SLA) plays a pivotal role, acting as the foundational document that sets the terms of engagement. The involvement of Service Management is central in orchestrating and coordinating these

steps. Furthermore, the integration of intent representations, service decomposition, policy frameworks, and service graphs demonstrates the meticulous planning and execution that underpin the establishment of a telecommunication service. The topology database and its role in providing accurate infrastructure information ensure that the service graph is aligned with the actual network configuration. Subsequently, testing and validation processes are carried out to ensure the reliability and performance of the newly created service. Finally, Service Management coordinates with Service Design to document the service comprehensively. This comprehensive process underscores the significance of effective communication and collaboration among various stakeholders to ensure the successful deployment of telecommunication services.

3.3. Intent-based Management of Network Slicing

3.3.1. Working Mechanism of SLA-intent Translation

The process of mapping involves connecting the contractual commitments and performance indicators specified in a SLA to the corresponding service/network intentions in service and network management. To begin, it is essential to fully understand the metrics and SLA criteria outlined in the contract, which define the specific goals that need to be achieved, such as performance, availability, or response times. Next, identify the service management layer intentions that align with the SLA requirements, which can include operational goals, duties, or actions that contribute to meeting the SLA objectives.

To establish a clear link between the SLA responsibilities and the operational activities within the service management layer, there is a need to map the SLA measurements and requirements to the appropriate service management layer intents. This may involve leveraging workflow automation tools, service orchestration platforms, or API interfaces to expedite the translation of SLA requirements into actionable activities that can be executed within the service management layer. It is important to track, evaluate, and report on the performance of the service management layer intents in relation to the SLA metrics. Regularly monitoring the progress, identifying deviations or non-compliance, and addressing any SLA breaches or performance gaps are crucial for maintaining alignment with the SLA objectives.

3.3.2. Intent-based management

Intent-based management is a process that starts by capturing users' high-level intentions and needs in a user-friendly language. These intentions are then translated and mapped to network-level intents, allowing the network infrastructure to understand and execute them. Through automation and orchestration, the network-level intents are seamlessly transformed into network device settings and commands, eliminating the need for manual translation, and reducing errors. Intent-based management ensures that the translated intentions align with the network's capabilities, with any inconsistencies being addressed through comments or recommendations. The system utilizes closed-loop control mechanisms to continuously monitor and adapt network behaviour, keeping it in line with the desired intentions. Real-time monitoring, analytics, and reporting are used to verify that the network achieves its goals, and appropriate actions are taken in case of network problems or performance concerns. Automation plays a vital role in expediting network changes, minimizing manual labour, and improving network flexibility and responsiveness.

3.3.3. Intent-based management for Transport domain

Following this intent-based networking philosophy, when network requests are eventually pushed to the transport network domain, they will have to be translated into the management of network slices or network partitions which will provide connectivity between the different grids that make up the DESIRE6G's environment.

To do so, we start from the service intent scheme described in previous sections. In those, we arrive at a configuration definition based on a series of SLAs and connectivity requests. These SLAs are translated as management intentions at the service level, and also must be passed to an operating domain level, and to an administrative domain. This process is depicted in Figure 5.

FIGURE 5. EXAMPLE OF INTENT-DRIVEN OPERATION FOR TRANSPORT DOMAINS.

At a transport domain level, what is asked for is a request of connectivity between two or more network points, reachable by the transport network to be configured. This network will also require some request metrics as bandwidth or latency. The metrics that will be able to receive the network controller will be agreed during the next stage. With these parameters, the Intent-based module will create a connection request that the transport SDN controller will be able to work with.

3.4. Hybrid container runtime

Deploying workloads in diverse infrastructure, with diverse requirements presents a challenge when the basic criteria range from security and isolation aspects to real-time instantiation and optimized execution performance. To this end, in DESIRE6G, we adopt a hybrid approach based on a custom container runtime and where we can differentiate the way services and applications are instantiated based on descriptors defined in the SMO.

3.4.1. Efficient Sandboxing of Containers on Edge Nodes

3.4.1.1. Containers and their benefits

Containers are lightweight, self-contained execution environments that encapsulate applications and their dependencies, providing a consistent and reproducible runtime environment. They enable the packaging of software in a manner that allows it to run reliably and consistently across different computing environments, including any computer hardware, infrastructure, or cloud environment. Achieving this versatility is made possible through a combination of operating system-level virtualization and resource isolation techniques. By leveraging kernel features, containers create isolated environments with their file systems, network interfaces, and process trees, ensuring application isolation from other containers and the host system. Moreover, containers abstract away the underlying infrastructure, allowing applications to be developed and deployed with minimal concern for specific hardware or software configurations. Unlike virtual machines, containers do not require a guest OS in each instance, resulting in smaller, faster, and highly portable units that can be executed on desktops, traditional IT systems, or in the cloud. By utilizing the features and resources of the host operating system, containers provide an efficient and platform-independent execution environment, making software deployment portable, scalable, and manageable across various environments, from development to production, on-premises, or in the cloud. Figure 6 shows a high-level overview of the node-level flow for a container spawn.

FIGURE 6. HIGH-LEVEL OVERVIEW OF GENERIC CONTAINER SPAWNING IN A K8S ENVIRONMENT

3.4.1.2. Limitations of containers

Despite their numerous advantages, containers have certain limitations, particularly in terms of security and isolation. Although containers provide a level of isolation by leveraging operating system features, they still share the underlying operating system kernel. This shared kernel introduces potential security risks, as a compromise within the kernel could impact the security and integrity of all containers running on the same host. Additionally, containers may not provide sufficient isolation for certain sensitive workloads or applications with strict security requirements. Furthermore, containers may face challenges when handling specific types of workloads, such as those with strict real-time requirements or resource-intensive applications that demand fine-grained control over hardware resources.

3.4.1.3. Sandboxing and its importance

To address the limitations of containers in terms of security, isolation and resource control, container sandboxing comes into play. By encapsulating containers within microVMs, each with its dedicated kernel instance, stronger isolation and security are achieved. The use of microVMs ensures that any compromise within a specific microVM remains contained, mitigating potential security risks from the shared underlying kernel. Moreover, container sandboxing resolves the insufficient isolation for sensitive workloads by providing a secure and isolated execution environment for individual containers within each microVM. With container sandboxing, containers can overcome their limitations in terms of security, isolation, and handling diverse workloads, making them more robust and suitable for a wide range of applications across various domains.

Figure 7 presents the high-level concept of container sandboxing using kata-containers.¹⁰

¹⁰ <https://katacontainers.io/>

FIGURE 7. CONTAINER SANDBOXING

Sandboxing in Edge Devices

Edge devices are computing devices positioned in proximity to where data is generated or consumed. Edge computing offers multiple advantages. Firstly, it reduces the need for data transfer to centralized locations, resulting in reduced network congestion and latency. Local data processing on edge devices enables faster response times, crucial for real-time. Secondly, edge devices enhance privacy and data security. Processing data locally minimizes the risk of data breaches during transmission, ensuring compliance with stringent privacy regulations. Lastly, edge devices improve reliability and availability. By distributing computing resources across multiple devices, the system becomes less reliant on centralized infrastructure, making it more resilient to network outages or connectivity issues.

Edge devices pose significant challenges in terms of limited computing resources and their heterogeneous nature. Firstly, edge devices often have constrained processing power, memory, and storage capacity, which can impact the performance and scalability of applications deployed on them. Secondly, the heterogeneous nature of edge devices introduces complexities. Different devices may have varying hardware capabilities, operating systems, and available hardware accelerators. This

requires developing specialized software that can seamlessly run across diverse edge devices, accommodating their unique characteristics. Developers must account for compatibility issues, adaptability, and the need for device-specific optimizations. In addition to these challenges, multitenancy adds another layer of complexity. When multiple deployments share the same edge devices, isolation becomes crucial to ensure the security and integrity of each application and its data. Sandboxing techniques, such as microVMs, can be employed to provide isolated execution environments for individual deployments, mitigating the risk of interference or unauthorized access.

Deploying multiple sandboxed containers in a single edge device can be challenging due to resource limitations and potential application conflicts. Edge devices often have constrained processing power, memory, and storage capacity, making it difficult to allocate sufficient resources to each container without impacting performance. Concurrently running multiple containers on the same device can lead to resource contention and interference, jeopardizing isolation and security.

Container orchestration platforms, like Kubernetes¹¹, provide advanced management capabilities for scaling and load balancing containers, ensuring efficient resource distribution. Lightweight virtualization technologies, such as specialized container runtimes and microVMs, enable isolation between containers and enhance security. By encapsulating each container's execution environment, sandboxing techniques mitigate interference and unauthorized access risks.

3.4.2. Sandboxed Containers

In the cloud environments and microservices age, containers have become very prominent, which is why we need to safeguard their execution while keeping their speed and portability intact. Kata Containers is an open-source project that aims to provide a secure and lightweight runtime environment for containerized applications. It leverages hardware virtualization technologies to offer strong separation between containers while maintaining the performance advantages of lightweight

¹¹ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/overview/>

containers. Launching a container in a micro VM, managed by a hypervisor, with its own kernel and root file system, ensures enhanced security and isolation, defending the application from remote execution, memory leaks, or unprivileged access, as well as protecting the host in case of untrusted or untested programs.

Table 1 summarizes the properties of various environments where processes run.

Type	Name	Virtualized	Rootfs	Rootfs device type	Mount type
Host	Host	No	Host specific	Host specific	Host specific
VM root	Guest (VM)	Yes	Rootfs inside the guest image	Hypervisor specific	ext4
VM container root	Container	Yes	Rootfs type requested by user	kataShared	virtioFS/ snapshotter

TABLE 1. PROCESS EXECUTION ENVIRONMENT

Kata Containers has a list of design requirements that its runtimes always guarantee to fulfil:

- OCI compatibility
- runc CLI compatibility
- CRI and Kubernetes support
- Multiple hardware architectures support
- Multiple hypervisor support
- Virtualization overhead reduction
- Networking & Storage compatibility
- I/O acceleration & scalability
- CI and structured logging

To address these requirements, the container runtime has been designed as a modular system, using various components, each with a unique task to actualize an end-to-end container spawn. The most prominent components are:

- Shim: Containered shimv2 implementation

- handles the shim process
- runs the ttRPC service in the shim side
- Service: services for containers
 - implements the ctr shim protocol and interacts with runtimes through messages.
- Runtimes: container runtimes
 - addresses messages from task services to manage containers.
 - contains the sandbox and the container manager.
- Resource: abstractions for resources
 - sandbox resources: network, share-fs
 - container resources: rootfs, volume, cgroup
- Hypervisor: manager for the VM
- Agent: used to communicate with the guest OS from the shim side

The runtime is compatible with the containerd¹² runtime shimv2 architecture and complies with the Open Container Initiative (OCI)¹³ runtime specification, making it Kubernetes-compatible with either CRI-O or the equivalent containerd implementation. A single runtime shim is also sufficient to manage all the OCI containers of an entire pod. Kata utilizes its agent, a daemon process, to establish robust communication between the guest and the host through a vsock socket operating on a ttRPC-based protocol. This approach enables the exchange of container management commands as well as carry the standard I/O streams between a container and its manager, eliminating also the need for multiple runtime calls. Such a structure ensures that Kata remains agnostic to the sandbox mechanisms, allowing a plethora of different hypervisors and different types of containers such as WebAssembly (Wasm) or Linux, not just virtualized ones, suiting different demands and preferences.

¹² <https://containerd.io/>

¹³ <https://opencontainers.org/>

3.4.3. Unikernels¹⁴ as Containers

To bridge the gap between containerized environments and unikernels, enabling seamless integration with cloud-native architectures, we introduce urunc. Designed to fully leverage the container semantics and benefit from the OCI tools and methodology, urunc aims to become “runc for unikernels”, while offering compatibility with the Container Runtime Interface (CRI). By relying on underlying hypervisors, urunc launches unikernels provided by OCI-compatible images, allowing developers and administrators to package, deliver, deploy, and manage their software using familiar cloud-native practices.

3.4.4. bima: unikernel container images

The first step to enable this functionality is to pack a unikernel into an OCI-compatible container image. To achieve this, we build *bima*, a software tool that embeds a unikernel image, metadata and its dependencies into a layered OCI container image. Figure 8 shows how to pack a unikernel image into an OCI-compatible container image, using *bima*.

FIGURE 8. PACKING A UNIKERNEL AS AN OCI-COMPATIBLE CONTAINER IMAGE

¹⁴ <http://unikernel.org/>

bima builds an OCI-compatible Container Image from a special type of Containerfile that supports a minimal set of instructions: FROM, COPY, and LABEL. The images built by bima are intended to be run by urunc, so there is no compatibility with other container runtimes. However, they can be pushed and pulled from generic container image registries, such as Docker Hub and on-premise Harbor installations.

- *FROM*: It is not taken into account in the current implementation, but we plan to add support for it.
- *COPY*: It works as in Dockerfiles. The current implementation supports only one copy operation per "instruction" (think one copy per line).
- *LABEL*: All LABEL "instructions" are added as annotations to the Container image. They are also added to a special urunc.json inside the container's rootfs.

Due to the tight coupling between bima and urunc, the few annotations required for urunc to work are also required by bima.

The required annotations are the following:

- *com.urunc.unikernel.unikernelType*: The type of the unikernel (can be rumprun, unikraft, etc)
- *com.urunc.unikernel.hypervisor*: The desired hypervisor to run the unikernel (e.g. qemu, hedge, hvt)
- *com.urunc.unikernel.binary*: The unikernel binary to run
- *com.urunc.unikernel.cmdline*: The cmdline used to run the unikernel

The produced image's platform OS is always Linux, while the platform architecture is automatically extracted from the ELF headers of the file defined in *com.urunc.unikernel.binary* annotation.

A sample Containerfile should look like the following code presented in Figure 9.

```
# the FROM instruction will not be parsed
FROM scratch

COPY test-redis.hvt /unikernel/test-redis.hvt
COPY redis.conf /conf/redis.conf

LABEL com.urunc.unikernel.binary=/unikernel/test-redis.hvt
```

```
LABEL "com.urunc.unikernel.cmdline"='{ "cmdline": "redis-server /data/conf/redis.conf", \
"net": { "if": "ukvmif0", "cloner": "True", "type": "inet", "method": "static", "addr": "10.0.66.2", "mask": "24", "gw": "10.0.66.1" }, \
"blk": { "source": "etfs", "path": "/dev/ld0a", "fstype": "blk", "mountpoint": "/data" } }'
LABEL "com.urunc.unikernel.unikernelType"="rumprun"
LABEL "com.urunc.unikernel.hypervisor"="qemu"
```

FIGURE 9. CONTAINER FILE SAMPLE

3.4.5. urunc¹⁵: a unikernel container runtime

Figure 10 presents a high-level architecture diagram of urunc and its interaction with the rest of the components in a generic container environment.

To delve into the inner workings of urunc, the process of starting a new unikernel “container” via containerd involves the following steps:

1. Containerd unpacks the image onto a devmapper block device and invokes urunc.
2. Urunc parses the image’s rootfs and annotations, initiating the required setup procedures. These include creating essential pipes for stdio and verifying the availability of the specified vmm.
3. Subsequently, urunc spawns a new process within a distinct network namespace and awaits the completion of the setup phase.
4. Once the setup is finished, urunc executes the vmm process, replacing the container’s init process with the vmm process. The parameters for the vmm process are derived from the unikernel binary and options provided within the “unikernel” image.
5. Finally, urunc returns the process ID (PID) of the vmm process to containerd, effectively enabling it to handle the container’s lifecycle management.

¹⁵ <https://github.com/nubificus/urunc>

FIGURE 10. RUNNING AN UNPACKED CONTAINER IMAGE AS A UNIKERNEL

Unikernels hold great potential for utilization in serverless deployments. With their lightweight nature, ultra-fast boot times, and singular purpose, unikernels align perfectly with the requirements of short-lived, single-purpose serverless functions. By leveraging urunc, developers can seamlessly deploy and manage unikernel-based serverless applications in a cloud-native manner. Combining unikernels and serverless computing enables efficient resource utilization, rapid scaling, and optimal performance, opening up possibilities for building highly efficient and responsive cloud-native applications.

Incorporating unikernels into the container ecosystem through urunc unlocks the benefits of both technologies. Unikernels provide better performance, security, and resource efficiency, while urunc enables seamless integration into cloud-native environments by embracing container semantics and OCI compatibility. This powerful combination empowers developers to leverage the advantages of unikernels while utilizing the robust orchestration capabilities, scalability, and ecosystem of cloud-native architectures.

3.5. Application-Layer Traffic Optimization

The Application-Layer Traffic Optimization (ALTO) Protocol is a network protocol standardized by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) that provides information about the network topology and the status of network resources based on metrics as the hops needed to access each node, the routing costs or the latency between each node.

ALTO protocol enables applications to make informed decisions on how to optimize the use of network resources and reduce congestion. For example, a video streaming application could use the ALTO protocol to obtain information about the location of content servers and select the server closest to the user with less traffic load at that moment. In this project, we are proposing the use of ALTO server to provide information about energy consumption, using this metric as the key one to decide between the different possibilities to connect different network points.

The ALTO protocol utilizes a client-server architecture, where applications act as clients and ALTO servers provide information about the network topology and available resources. ALTO servers can be implemented at various points in the network. This scheme is represented in Figure 11.

FIGURE 11. BASIC ALTO ARCHITECTURE (FROM RFC7285)

The results provided by ALTO are represented as two JSON maps: the *networkmap* and the *costmap*, both represented in the Figure 12. The first of these two maps, shows the different networks reachable by the nodes that conforms the monitored topology. On the other hand, the second one shows the cost of reaching from one node to another. This representation is similar to a matrix in which the diagonal is 0 and there may not be symmetric.

FIGURE 12. NETWORKMAP AND COSTMAP EXAMPLES

The ALTO protocol is independent of the underlying network technology and can be used in different types of networks, including local area networks (LANs), wide area networks (WANs), and the Internet. This characteristic is basic for our implementation in the Desire6G context: As it does not depend on a certain technology, it can work in a new generation architecture obtaining information from different sources. This information is not recollected directly from devices (ALTO does not monitor the devices), therefore it would need a recollection module to do so. In Desire6G context we are working with the next two information sources:

- Transport topology Information. This information shows the transport topology that connects the different MAS agents. The protocol agreed to be used to do so is BGP [8]. The information to be exposed through the BGP speakers will be agreed during the next stage of Desire6G.
- Data Centres Information. In order to identify the network computational nodes available to deploy the network functions and their capabilities ALTO needs to be fed with this information. These capabilities need to be well known by the Desire6G system and stores somewhere. ALTO will use the information stored and relates them with the topological information obtained from BGP speakers.

The integration with both information sources (i.e., BGP speaker and Topology Database) should be agreed as ALTO provides the transport topology information but does not collect it.

There are two potential uses for the abstraction view provided by ALTO. On the one hand, ALTO could be instantiated as a NBI from MAS systems to provide a transport topological view to the SDN controller showing the information extracted from the BGP speakers. On the other hand, ALTO could be instantiated in the SMO as a topology exposure module that feeds the MLFO. This last behaviour is represented in Figure 13.

FIGURE 13. ALTO SERVER INTERACTION WITH MLFO MODULE.

The presence of ALTO could bring the benefits of applying an abstraction and digest process in order to expose this information to a network client or to a module that could require a completed view of the network under management. In the Desire6G case, what we propose is the use of ALTO maps to feed the Artificial Intelligence that will take decisions about how to distribute the network functions. These maps will provide a complete but simplified view of the transport network status, focusing on the power consumption metric and latency.

3.6. DLT federation

Nowadays, service providers are confronted with the challenge of satisfying the needs of both their vertical customers and end users. To accomplish this, they must effectively dimension and manage their

infrastructure, which includes various computing, storage, and networking devices, to fit the expected demand. In situations where there is an infrastructure failure (e.g., burned data centre) or a sudden increase of the number of users for a specific service (e.g., concerts, football games), service providers often struggle to react on time to keep a service operational. In these scenarios, virtualization offers a cost-effective and time-efficient solution. Instead of expanding their local infrastructure, it is more practical for an operator to use services and/or resources owned by other operators/providers. This approach provides numerous advantages such as environmental benefits, reduced operational costs for the lessee, and the capability to fulfil user requirements promptly without encountering penalties. This concept, called *federation*, enables operators to orchestrate services and resources from external administrative domains. Federation has already been explored within the context of network function virtualization (NFV)-based platforms, with a particular focus on expanding the management and orchestration (MANO) stack to enable federation of services and resources. While there may be slight variations in the definition of federation, a common assumption is the existence of a pre-established agreement among service providers. However, reaching such agreements is time-consuming and suitable only for static environments. The goal of the DLT federation building block of the SMO is to explore how blockchain technology can complement NFV MANO service providers to accomplish federation in dynamic scenarios such as the on-demand deployment of virtual point of access to extend the user radio coverage.

In the following paragraphs, we describe the execution of the federation process and the contemporary challenges it faces, discuss how blockchain as a DLT can enhance it, and elaborate on how the DLT federation aligns within the SMO architecture.

3.6.1. Service federation procedures

There are several steps that administrative domains (ADs) need to follow in order to successfully complete a service federation:

- **Registration** - Initial procedure through which the ADs establish their peer-to-peer interconnectivity or register to a central entity. The *registration* procedure defines the nature of the federation, which can be relatively open or strictly closed. An open federation allows for

easier registration of external domains to engage in peer-to-peer or centralized interaction. On the other hand, a closed federation involves pre-defined participants with stringent policies and rules that are manually established and defined by the ADs.

- **Discovery** - During this step, the participating ADs periodically broadcast or exchange among themselves information on their capabilities to provide services. By sharing and exchanging this information, a consumer AD can gather a comprehensive overview of the available services within the federation.
- **Announcement** - This procedure is triggered by the consumer domain, once it has been decided to federate part of a service in an external peering domain. In that case, an offer announcement is broadcast to all potential provider ADs, including the specific requirements for a particular service.
- **Negotiation** - When the potential provider ADs receive the announced offer, analyze whether they can fulfill the stated requirements and respond with either a positive or negative answer. In the case of a positive response, they also provide the pricing details for the service.
- **Acceptance and Deployment** - The consumer AD collects all positives responses and selects a single provider domain's offer. The final decision is made by the consumer AD using internal policy criteria. Once a decision is made, the consumer domain sends an acceptance reply to the chosen provider AD. Following that, the "winning" provider AD proceeds with the deployment of the requested federated service.
- **Usage and Charging** - After successful deployment, the provider AD notifies the consumer AD and shares all the essential details required for integrating the federated service into the end-to-end service deployment. Subsequently, the provider AD starts charging for the federated service during its life-cycle, until it is terminated. Note that the provider AD has a "kill switch" or the ability to terminate the federation at any point in time.

3.6.2. Federation challenges

Next, we provide an overview of the main challenges associated with multi-domain federation in dynamic environments (Table 2), identifying how these challenges are addressed based on their interconnection approach. We subsequently emphasize how blockchain as a technology can serve as a

fundamental solution to these challenges, but we first focus on how this is currently done for the centralized and decentralized-peering types of solutions:

- **Admission Control.** In an open federation, administrative domains have the freedom to join or leave at any time. In a centralized interconnection model, a central authority manages admission control, deciding which domains are allowed to join or leave the network. In contrast, with a decentralized-peering approach, the access can be completely open depending on each individual AD. In both cases, the main challenge is to balance the trade-off between domain openness and preserving privacy, security, and trust. Highly secure frameworks and message exchanges may introduce higher delays or congestion in the federation interaction, while completely open admission could expose ADs to passive spoofing.
- **Availability.** The number of participating ADs changes over time in dynamic environments. Centralized approaches offer easier monitoring of participants but may introduce inconsistencies if there are sporadic failures, as centralized systems are susceptible to single points of failure. This can lead to the federation becoming unavailable. Decentralized-peering solutions inherently provide more resilience to failures, but the task of tracking the ADs is more complex and may introduce spoofing risks.
- **Dynamic pricing and billing.** ADs seek to increase profits by adjusting the federation price offerings, especially in dynamic environments. A central entity, acting as an auctioneer, can modify federation offerings and oversee the billing process. However, participating domains must voluntarily trust this federation control and pay for it. In the decentralized-peering scenario, the ADs autonomously set the price offerings. The challenge here lies in quickly establishing secure agreements in the form of dynamic SLAs that serve as a baseline for reliable billing. Additionally, implementing mechanisms to identify other domains and securely handle the charging process is costly.
- **Multi-domain quality of service (QoS).** Ensuring QoS across federating domains is particularly challenging in dynamic environments. Both decentralized-peering and decentralized-distributed approaches encounter difficulties in establishing dynamic SLAs and maintaining unbiased monitoring data. Disagreements on monitored data among domains often lead to disputes,

requiring third-party entities for SLA monitoring. In the centralized option, a centralized entity is responsible for establishing QoS across domains, controlling and monitoring the entire process.

- **Security and privacy.** Within a centralized interconnection model, ADs rely on the central entity. To enhance security, the central entity might request more information from each AD, which comes at the cost of reduced privacy per domain. On the other hand, a decentralized-peering solution may achieve higher privacy (exchanging less information with peering domains) at the cost of lower-security policies employed.

Challenges	Interconnections		
	Centralized	Decentralized peering	Blockchain
Admission control	Central	Open	Distributed; consensus voting
Availability	High single point of failure	Unknown; fail-safe	Balanced; fail-safe; Incentive to participate
Dynamic pricing and billing	Central auctioneer; single-point control	Autonomous; no control; no billing	Autonomous by default; token-based billing
Multi-domain QoS	Central control and monitoring (dynamic SLAs)	None	Smart contract as dynamic SLAs; off-chain oracles
Security and privacy	High security; low privacy	Low security; high privacy	High security; high privacy

TABLE 2. FEDERATION CHALLENGES

3.6.3. Federation using DLT (blockchain + smart contract)

Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs) such as Blockchain can be seen as a secure and failure-resistant platform for both negotiation and execution of service federation. The main advantages of applying blockchain in networking encompass:

- **Security.** The transaction data within each block of the blockchain is timestamped, tamper-proof, and immutable. Any attempts to modify the data would require the collaboration of at least 51% of the nodes being malicious or compromised.
- **Integrity, and trust.** All participants can easily verify the state of the blockchain by confirming that they have observed an equivalent state of the blockchain.

- **Smart Contracts.** Programmable applications that run as autonomous entities or members and are built on top of a blockchain platform, such as Ethereum. These applications contain predefined rules and conditions that automatically execute and enforce transactions or actions when specific conditions are met. This functionality enables them to incorporate business logic and rules, similar to traditional contract agreements.
- **Privacy and transparency.** All transactions, state transitions, and block creations are transparent. Using cryptography, private data can be encrypted and kept confidential while still preserving the specified transition rules.
- **Third-party absence.** The consensus mechanism enables a trustworthy collaboration among anonymous members, eliminating the need for a third-party authority to guarantee the integrity of the participants.

Just by looking at the main characteristics of blockchain technology mentioned earlier, most of the federation challenges enumerated in Table 2 can be addressed by deploying a non-customized (vanilla) version of a permissioned blockchain network (Ethereum, Hyperledger, Cosmos, etc).

Admission control relies on the blockchain governance policy. Permissioned blockchains typically involve member acceptance through voting. While some domains may act maliciously and reject the entry of new members, they generally have an incentive to increase participation. If it is not the case, multiple blockchain instances may run in parallel.

Availability is ensured through each domain's incentive to maintain an active blockchain node. Consequently, this enhances the network security (avoiding 51 percent attacks) and increases the domain's usage budget (e.g., gas in Ethereum). In the event of a node failure, departure, or compromise, the blockchain network remains operational, and the domain can access it via other nodes using its unique blockchain address.

Security and privacy are established by restricting the usage budget and employing cryptography. Newly joined domains have limited usage budgets or a restricted number of federation announcements, preventing them from spoofing or spamming other participating domains. Communications between

domains are recorded as immutable transactions on the ledger, with cryptography for preserving data privacy.

Dynamic pricing, billing, and multi-domain QoS require the implementation of dynamic SLAs and QoS monitoring. A promising approach for achieving this integration involves the use of smart contracts. The ETSI PDL¹⁶ specification hints at this approach by describing a scenario where smart contracts represent a specific service with QoS metrics in a marketplace of SLAs. Customers ready to deploy a service from the marketplace must send a payment blockchain transaction to the corresponding smart contract. An external entity acts as an oracle to monitor QoS metrics and record SLA fulfilment directly in the smart contract. If QoS standards are not met, the smart contract automatically issues a blockchain payment transaction to the customer's blockchain address including the penalty amount. Additionally, service providers, acting as smart contract owners, can dynamically adjust prices in each smart contract before customers make deposit transactions.

3.6.4. DLT-based federation in SMO

14 shows our proposal of applying blockchain to open federation in SMO domains. An administrative domain is the service provider with the SMO infrastructure. We propose the installation of a blockchain node within each domain infrastructure with a direct connection on the Eastbound/Westbound interface of the SMO. By adding and registering a node, the administrative domains gain access to the blockchain network. We argue that maintaining this decoupling enables the independent evolution of both NFV and blockchain technologies. Our designed solution involves the creation of a new smart contract for every new federation of services or resources. These smart contracts represent dynamic federation SLAs that guarantee the QoS between the consumer and provider domains. The focus in the

¹⁶ https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gr/PDL/001_099/021/01.01.01_60/gr_PDL021v010101p.pdf

smart contract design is to ensure neutrality and privacy while overseeing the federation procedures that involves all ADs.

FIGURE 14. DLT FEDERATION FOR THE SMO

The proposed workflow for a DLT service federation process is illustrated in Figure 15. We assume that the DLT network is already set up, with a compiled and deployed Federation Smart Contract (SC). Additionally, a service is running under the consumer AD and is being monitored by the monitoring component of the SMO, which tracks its KPIs.

ADs interested in participating in the federation process must first register in the smart contract (step 1). Note that the domains communicate with each other using the DLT network through the service orchestrator component of the SMO. Once registered, they can participate as consumers or providers.

When the monitoring component of the consumer AD identifies that the KPIs of the active service are not being met, it alerts the service orchestrator about the need for federation (step 2). Next, the service orchestrator in the consumer AD creates and sends an announcement (or federation offer) to the Federation SC as a transaction (step 3). This announcement includes the specific requirements of the desired deployment. The Federation SC records the announcement as a new auction on the blockchain and broadcasts it to all registered ADs (step 4). It is important to note that the address of the consumer AD is hidden in the broadcast announcement to protect its privacy and prevent other ADs from passively collecting information.

Once the broadcast announcement is received, potential providers analyze the requirements and place a bid offer with the Federation SC (step 5), specifying the service price. The Federation SC records each received offer and forwards them to the consumer AD (step 6). The consumer AD then selects a suitable provider AD (e.g., provider X) and closes the auction in the Federation SC (step 7). The winning provider is recorded by the Federation SC, which immediately broadcasts a message to all participating ADs that the federation announcement is finished and a winner has been chosen (step 8). This marks the end of the negotiation and acceptance phases.

The winning provider AD proceeds with the deployment of the requested federated service (step 9). This deployment process, which involves service instantiation, is elaborated in prior section 3.

After successful deployment, the provider AD confirms the operation by sending a transaction to the Federation SC (step 10), which includes relevant service information such as connection details. The Federation SC records the successful deployment of the federated service and notifies the consumer AD (step 11). The consumer AD utilizes the operational federated service until it is needed, then terminates the service through the Federation SC.

FIGURE 15 WORKFLOW DIAGRAM FOR DLT SERVICE FEDERATION PROCESS

4. Multi-Agent System

Autonomous network operation is required to deal with the expected large traffic dynamicity and provide the stringent performance required by beyond 5G and 6G services. Solutions for autonomous operation running in a centralized controller/orchestrator have the potential to greatly reduce costs, but they might lead to inefficient resource utilization because of their long response times. To minimize response time, control algorithms might be executed as close as possible to the data sources.

Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) is a subfield of AI, and it can be defined as a set of individual agents that share knowledge and communicate with each other in order to solve a problem that is beyond the scope of a single agent. In the scope of networking, agents can make autonomous decisions near-real-time based on guidelines received from a centralized orchestrator, thus liberating the orchestrator from near-real-time operations. In this project, we propose a MAS making per-service decisions. The system autonomously makes decisions, e.g., related to routing of the packet flows considering the measured e2e delay, but without previous knowledge of traffic characteristics because of its ability to learn.

In addition, using AI/ML algorithms for service automation entails analysing heterogeneous data collected from monitoring points in network devices. Because services can be reconfigured, e.g., flow rerouting, it is of paramount importance to link different AI/ML functions (i.e., performance data collection, analysis, control, storage, etc.) among them to create an AI/ML pipeline and to the related service. AI/ML pipelines are associated to network entities and need to be deployed and reconfigured using an independent orchestrator, named ML Function Orchestrator (MLFO), known as ITU-ML [18].

Finally, AI/ML pipelines and inter agent communication in the MAS show a distributed attack surface. To overcome their software higher security exposure, we combine a set of scalable techniques fostering enhanced security applied on individual agents and their communications. Specifically, the proposed solution combines: i) binary hardening with secure execution monitoring; ii) distributed ledger technologies for non-real-time MAS management; and iii) VXLAN and encrypted communications for near real-time MAS operation. The solution is designed not only to provide strong security to the MAS, but also to minimize any functional overhead.

4.1. MAS architecture

Agents are software entities controlling the operation of a specific service spanning through different network segments (e.g., radio access network and packet switches). The internal architecture of an agent in the DESIRE6G MAS approach is presented in Figure 16, which consists of five main components: i) a *manager module* configuring and supervising the operation of the rest of the modules; ii) a *security manager* in charge of security aspects, like key management; iii) a number of *algorithms* for data processing that include dimensionality reduction, data veracity checking, and QoS assurance; iv) a number of *interfaces* to communicate with other systems. Additionally, interfaces take care of the security of communications, e.g., to ensure data privacy, authentication, and integrity; and v) a Redis¹⁷ DB that is used in publish-subscribe mode to communicate the different modules among them, i.e., no direct communication is allowed. This facilitates the definition of specific workflows for telemetry data and provides an agile, reliable, and secure environment that simplifies communication, as well as integration of new modules.

Among the interfaces, we can distinguish some general ones, starting from MAS management, telemetry, data plane control, and inter-MAS communication:

- For management purposes, a REST interface is exposed to connect the agents to the SMO.
- For telemetry, external data sources are connected to the telemetry agent through a dedicated interface (e.g., based on gRPC¹⁸). Only trusted peers are allowed to connect externally to the telemetry agent. In addition, a gRPC interface is used for the telemetry agents to export telemetry to the monitoring service in the SMO.
- For control, dedicated interfaces will connect with different elements in the technological domains, e.g., the near-real-time controller in the RAN, the SDN controller and the packet nodes

¹⁷ <https://redis.io/>

¹⁸ <https://grpc.io/>

in the transport network, and the virtual infrastructure manager (VIM) in the Computing and Storage infrastructure.

- Inter-agent communication is based on REST interfaces.

FIGURE 16. ARCHITECTURE OF THE MAS AGENTS

Figure 17 presents a preliminary view of the MAS for service management and the interfaces to the rest of the system in the DESIRE6G architecture. Specifically, the interfaces are:

- O2M (OSM to MAS): this interface includes:
 - OSM->MAS: Configuration of the MAS agent, e.g., id of the service, QoS parameters to be ensured, addresses of the rest of the MAS agents for that service, addresses and characteristics of data plane control elements, secret keys, resources allocated for the service, etc.
 - MAS->OSM: resource management, QoS related notifications, etc.
 - Telemetry measurements and other statistics.
- S2M (SDN to MAS): this interface includes:
 - SDN->MAS: resources allocated for the service
 - MAS->SDN: resource management, QoS related notifications, etc.
- M2X (MAS to xApp) / M2P (MAS to Packet Node) / M2V (MAS to VIM): these interfaces include:
 - MAS->X: Resource control

- Telemetry measurements
- A2A (MAS Agent to MAS Agent). This interface includes:
 - Telemetry measurements, notifications, models, etc. exchanged among agents.

Interfaces O2M, S2M, and A2A are encrypted using IPsec over a VXLAN tunnel created at service provisioning time. For clarity, in the Figure 17, MAS refers to a MAS agent.

FIGURE 17. MAS FOR SERVICE MANAGEMENT AND RELATED INTERFACES

4.2. Machine Learning Function Orchestrator

This section presents a preliminary architecture of Machine Learning Function Orchestrator (MLFO) as well as includes algorithms for managing AI/ML pipelines, including its computation and reconfiguration.

Many intent-based applications might focus on the operation of one single network entity, where the source of monitoring data and the point of actuation are closely related, e.g., a packet node. However, generally speaking, intent-based applications require a global view of the network resources. A very natural application is for failure localization, where data needs to be collected from heterogeneous sources and analysed together. Based on the definition in [18], in this section, we present a MLFO architecture as an independent orchestrator that manages AI/ML pipelines by placing AI/ML functions in different locations in the network and connecting them to create a chain.

AI/ML Pipeline Management

Let us first focus on the AI/ML Pipeline computation through a realistic sample. For illustrative purposes, let us assume that a service data plane requires deploying MAS, which includes an AI/ML pipeline with five different ML functions: *i*) collector (*Co*) in charge of collecting monitoring data from activated monitoring points (*M*), e.g., from packet switches; *ii*) aggregator (*Ag*) that collects measurements from a number of different collectors and perform some not computationally intensive task, like compute some statistics, e.g., max, min, and average; *iii*) processor (*Pr*), which performs more computational intensive task on the received data; *iv*) a time series database (*DB*); and *v*) a user interface (*UI*). The relation among those AI/ML functions can be specified as a graph $T=(V,A)$ as shown in Figure 18 (a) below.

FIGURE 18. AI/ML PIPELINE TEMPLATE (A), DEPLOYMENT (B) AND RECONFIGURATION (C).

An optimization problem can be defined to find the optimal solution, given graph T , the description of the set of nodes N , the constraints for the set of arcs A , as well as some other constraints, like fixed AI/ML function placements. The output of the problem should include the placement of the AI/ML

functions to create an AI/ML pipeline that follows template T and meets the constraints, while minimizing some utility function (e.g., number and capacity of containers/VMs to be deployed, connectivity cost, etc.) subject to the state of the resources in the infrastructure. We name such problem *AI/ML Pipeline Deployment* (PLD) and it can formally be stated as:

Given:

- *Pipeline Template*: graph $T = (V, A)$, where $V = \{\text{allowed types}=\{type\}\}$, $A = \{\text{maxDelay, minCapacity}\}$, and $type=\langle\text{container/VM descriptor, fan-out}\rangle$.
- *Constrained nodes*: set $N = \{n, F\}$, where $n = type \in v$ "allowed types" $\mid v \in V$, and F is a set of constraints, e.g., a location, and it can be empty.
- Infrastructure, i.e., edge/cloud computing and connectivity.

Output: The pipeline P to be deployed, i.e., $P = (N', E) \sim T$, $N' \supseteq N$ and every $e \in E$ is an instance of $a \in A$ that satisfies its constraints.

Objective: Minimize some utility function.

To solve the PLD problem, a heuristic algorithm can be developed to place the constrained ML functions and find the shortest paths connecting the already placed AI/ML functions. During such process, more AI/ML functions can be added to meet the given constraints until graph P following template T is obtained. An example of solution is illustrated in Figure 18 (b), where the location of the collector AI/ML functions have been specified to be in the same location as the related monitoring point (M). Once the PLD problem is solved, the obtained solution needs to be deployed.

Because the AI/ML pipeline is linked to an entity in the data plane, when that entity is reconfigured, its AI/ML pipeline might also need to be reconfigured. Therefore, we can define a different optimization problem, where we are given the template T , the current AI/ML pipeline P and the new set of constrained nodes and the objective is to reconfigure P with the minimum cost (e.g., number of changes in P' with respect to P and the total cost, etc.). We name such problem *AI/ML Pipeline Reconfiguration* (PLR) and it can be stated as:

Given:

- The template T , the deployed pipeline P and the new set of constrained nodes N .
- Infrastructure, i.e., edge/cloud computing and connectivity.

Output: The new pipeline P' to be deployed.

Objective: Minimize some utility function.

A heuristic similar as the one for the PLD problem can be devised, where the deployed AI/ML functions that are not in the new constrained set of nodes are first removed, and the nodes that need to be migrated are disconnected and moved. An example of reconfiguration is presented in Figure 18 (c), where AI/ML function Co2 is not needed for the new AI/ML pipeline, and Co3 and Co4 have been added. The MLFO exposes an East/West bond Interface that can be used to trigger the deployment of AI/ML pipelines. The deployment request includes an AI/ML pipeline *descriptor*, which includes the template, constrained nodes, etc. The MLFO runs the PLD and PLR optimization problems to compute the AI/ML pipeline to be deployed (*deployment plan*), and coordinates with the orchestrator. A specific VLAN is created for each AI/ML pipeline for intra-DC communications, whereas we rely on VXLAN tunnels to connect AI/ML functions in different locations.

4.3. MAS SECURITY

4.3.1. Agent exposure and security needs

With their direct 6G service monitoring and control abilities, MAS agents are threats of choice and highly exposed, typically to forge denial of service attacks. Agents shall be secured by-design to be resilient against confidentiality, integrity and availability attacks, during deployment and their runtime. More, the MAS concept is based on inter-agent collaboration, which calls for trust between agents. Trust shall be first derived from the standard remote attestation, assuring that agents to talk with are what they are supposed to be. Moreover, trust can be enriched by dynamic trustworthiness collected metrics as an agent can still be corrupted after its last attestation. To meet the goal of maintaining trust over time, a runtime monitoring of the agent's healthy condition shall be set. Last, the communications between two trusted agents shall be secured.

To bridge these different security needs, two main technologies will be leveraged:

- i. TAGES automatic executable rewriting tool, to create hardened, authenticable and self-monitored agents.
- ii. Permissioned DLT (with associated smart contract) to orchestrate remote attestations and runtime metrics collection, stores their results and give access to communication keys. The associated processes are non-real time executed.
- iii. Inter-agent communication shall be protected using VxLAN¹⁹ and IPSec²⁰ protocols. Key exchanges are executed in near real time taking advantage of the DLT.

In view of the above requirements, the DESIRE6G solution for securing MAS is sketched in Figure 19 based on the following ingredients: A) SECaaS binary hardening, B) secure execution monitoring based on hardening, C) DLT orchestrated non real time security functions over the network and D) near real-time MAS operation (key exchange).

4.3.2. Agent security by-design by SECaaS

As shown in Figure 19, By automatic agent rewriting, the SECaaS hardens the agents against various threats and installs new enablements for the security of the agents. As an illustration to these enablements, the SECaaS installs the software primitives needed for the mutual attestation scheme, transforming each agent into a potential verifier and prover. The agents are on one hand hardened for their self-protection and on the other side, taking part of a collective security scheme. Both self-protection and collective security modifications on the executable files are processed through the SECaaS which consumes executable files and delivers protected executable files. Different types of security bearing are considered in DESIRE6G, implemented with different maturity level (TRL). The analysis of the agents security is enumerated through the CIA threat model (Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability) to which we add cloning and vulnerability based attacks. The associated threat models

¹⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Virtual_Extensible_LAN

²⁰ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/rfc6071/>

and corresponding mitigations are enumerated in Table 3 below, presenting details on the threat, the associated mitigation and the soundness of the mitigation. Mitigation trustworthiness is delivered over two levels (i.e., full, relative). Table 3 features the status of the SECaaS at DESIRE6G project start, while Table 4 details the evolutions which are considered in the performance of the project.

FIGURE 19. GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF AGENT SECURITY

Attack	Threat model-use case	SECaaS hardening mitigation (details)	Mitigation soundness
Confidentiality loss (for intellectual property loss or vulnerability search)	Static (i.e., analysis of executable file) or dynamic (i.e., analysis on DRAM pages).	<p>Encryption of SW .so or .exe text section (ie, instructions)</p> <p>Control flow shadowing de-structures the software call graph, offering a relatively good obfuscation potency at low performance impact.</p>	<p>Full</p> <p>Relative</p>
Tampering	Modify agent before on-boarding or during execution	<p>Self-authentication verification by the executable before jumping to its entrypoint, using a reference signature delivered by the SECaaS, the appended measurement and verification primitives. Optional leverage of Intel’s SGX TEE for these elements for higher security.</p> <p>Periodic integrity self-checks at runtime using the initial memory footprint and according to two implementations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The verification routine can be tampered itself (inversion of the test) 2. Optional leverage of Intel’s SGX TEE 	<p>Full in TEE, at measure. Relative without TEE and between two measures (ToCToU) attacks.</p>
Cloning	Collect and install software on attacker controlled platform	Two elementary solutions with the selective provisioning of the AES key or the RSA public key used for self-authentication on validated platforms	Relative

TABLE 3 SECURITY ENFORCEMENT OF CURRENT SECAAS

In addition, further developments on the SECaaS can reach the following security properties as listed in Table 4 below.

Attack	Threat model-use case	SECaaS hardening mitigation (details)	Mitigation soundness
Tampering	Modify agent before on-boarding or during execution	Mutual attestation as considered for agent remote attestation consists in injecting the measurement and the verification primitives and their APIs for being called upon events.	Full in TEE and at measurement time. Relative without TEE and/or between two measures (ToCToU) attacks. By separating the prover and the verifier, mutual attestation trustworthiness is higher than self-attestation.
Cloning	Collect and install software on attacker controlled platform	The SECaaS can bind the agent’s SW on a secret provisioned platform (or set of trusted) with several flavors and trust levels . An advanced implementation creates a semantic dependency on the rewritten software to a platform-provisioned secret.	Several levels (according to binding mechanisms)
Agent availability ROP-JOP (Return-Jump Oriented Programming)	Targeted attack on victim software by co-resident SW (e.g., ROP, DoS)	Runtime Control Flow monitoring, collecting per code block time-frequency series, monitoring the performance and correct execution of the agent delivering: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Proof of execution 2. Proof of normal execution (compared to a normal execution pattern) 	Full Relative

TABLE 4. SECURITY ENFORCEMENT FROM SECAAS DEVELOPMENTS

4.3.3. Inter-agent trust building

Remote attestation is the first requirement to be met, ensuring that any inter-agent communication does not convey data from or to a corrupted agent, potentially able of all forms of attacks. For scalability,

DESIRE6G develops a software-based, hence infra-agnostic attestation model, removing hardware and middleware dependencies. No dependency means that agents shall be totally self-efficient for the task which yields to mutual attestation model, where agents are capable to measure themselves (i.e., to prove themselves) and verify a peer's prove. The mutual attestation scheme exploits a DLT structure to (1) elect the most trustworthy agent to verify an identified peer agent, (2) store the remote attestation result in the immutable and shared block chained perpetual duplicated storage. Once implemented, this DLT-backed mutual attestation will be incrementally enriched to collect novel correctness evidence from runtime execution traces. For that, a self-monitoring capacity shall be developed with logs gradually collected during the execution but used in a transitory manner upon a given external trigger.

4.3.4. DLT relevance for MAS security:

We have apprehended and somehow challenges the relevance of using a DLT layout for MAS security, aiming at finding the best match (i.e., best use) of it for a coupling it with the executable rewriting SECaaS. Preliminary works were quickly initiated in the early weeks of the project start inside the consortium for the submission of a conceptual publication [3] and leveraging prior works inside the consortium [1] [2].

This initial study work has brought to us a more mature understanding of the most relevant use cases for DLT leverage as well as the associated intricacies. The main benefits in the perspective of DLT use for a MAS lattice are given as (i) **Immutability** of the DLT transactions states. MAS agents control the network, their decision takings (i.e., a MAS security transaction) permits liability awareness, incident forensics and root cause analysis and traceability, (ii) **Distributed security** with no central point of attack-failure. DLT-backed agents erect stronger security as a function of quantity, therefore more than one agent can bring, (iii) **Separate channel** from the network. The DLT lattice has no connection to the network core pipes, acting as a separate channel ingesting metadata, (iii) **Programmability**: Smart contracts are programmable business logic, customized protocols issuing network-orchestration related transactions (i.e., resource management, routing and node instantiation decision-taking). Smart contracts flexibility enables to program our own rules and to modify them dynamically.

Our investigation has revealed the disparate nature of MAS agents, which are locality dependent, as they act locally, at their physical position to monitor and control specific type of resource (e.g., radio head, edge). For doing that, agents feature different semantics (i.e., adapted to a specific network resource

type) and they cannot interact with another resource located here or elsewhere. Resource and locality dependent agents are not interchangeable, hence cannot be orchestrated through DLT-back service federation, electing a doer from a community of equally capable peers. However, this condition can be obtained when one single function is appended to all agents, all able to execute this specific function. The SECaaS can be used to add one common functions to all agents and they are the Prove and Verify primitives of the mutual attestation protocol. We have considered several consensus types in our study phase [4][5] to find the most adapted one to our usage.

4.3.5. Federation of service for mutual remote attestation.

Service federation can be used for mutual attestation model for the verification function so that any agent can verify a peer's measurement. Each agent would then be able to produce its own measure (i.e. or prove itself) and verify a peer's proof. Agents are different; hence their memory footprint hashes are. The hash references shall be provisioned to the verifiers and used for their equality check, timely. This reference measurement supply service is incumbent upon the DLT and a smart contract. Mutual attestation model is a nascent interesting area of research which fits well with the distributed nature of MAS lessening if not cancelling single point of failure risks derived from a centralized remote attestation verification function. For this essential reason, DLT-backed mutual attestation has been considered by academics in the field of IoT [6][7]. The first elements of comparison with DESIRE6G agent mutual attestation solution concerns the measured element and second how the measurement references are originated and provisioned. In the IoT context, the measured elements are the static IoT firmware and application, which result from the IoT device vendor. Conversely, DESIRE6G deals with functionality-versatile agents. The variability is magnified with the building of singular artifacts for each unique deployment of the same agent. In our implementation, the signatures are generated by the SECaaS which can be interfaced to feed these signatures when they are needed.

Our design space has integrated the following considerations of (1) scalability, (2) performance, (3) convergence and integration with other MAS security DLT-backed services **Scalability** has been considered on two different aspects of deployment constraints and storage requirement. The formerly cited DLT-backed remote attestation solutions are infrastructure dependent as requiring neither a TPM, hybrid anchoring technology nor software attestation primitive on the IoT firmware. Our work differs

from this approach, stemming for a platform-agnostic deployment, by use of our binary rewriting SECaaS which directly affix the attestation verify and prove routines in each agent. Blockchain store requirement: When a DLT blocks log is shared and duplicated at different locations and by nature of blockchain can only grow at each block creation, the block size shall be limited. We have considered that a remote attestation transaction or block shall only contain the identifiers of the measured and verifying agents, the time of the measure and the result of the verification test (i.e., 1 bit size).

- **Performance** will be further elaborated with field and real performance measure, coming naturally at the end of our implementation. However, we have considered the main aspects of reducing the resource burden of the DLT by following at first the semi-distributed structure which sets a node for a variable quantity of agents and not at each agent, in alignment with DESIRE6G choice. Another area of consideration will be to check the reality of the timing requirement for the measurement. In replacement of the event-triggered measurement process, de-synchronized measurements could be done at the best time or in best efforts, releasing the costs on the processor.
- **Convergence with the Key exchange DLT structure.** Without being a firm requirement, our first selection of the DLT and smart contract is aligned with the key exchange DLT and smart contract. These elements are a private blockchain by Go Ethereum²¹, web3.py²² and node.js-truffle²³ for interacting with the block chain and smart contract. Another important point is the use of the Docker²⁴ containerization which simply removes the burden of injecting the software inside the executable of the agent as was considered previously. This shortcut may eventually prove to be inadequate during the implementation.

²¹ <https://ethereum.org/en/>

²² <https://pypi.org/project/web3/>

²³ <https://nodejs.org/en>

²⁴ <https://www.docker.com/>

4.3.6. DLT-backed Mutual Remote Attestation sequencing

At first, it is important to recall that our solution shall be applied to agents taken as is and in a context where no attestation framework exists or be pre-installed. The first initial step is to “wrap” these agents for embedding them with the attestation abilities. This is done at the SECaaS which also stores for each agent its attestation reference measurement which will be transferred timely and selectively to a verifier. For that the smart contract node can access to the SECaaS reference measurement store.

At the receipt of a ‘trust contract’ from the SMO which establish that two agents will be collaborating and require mutual trust, the smart contract will initiate the bi-directional mutual attestation which results in that both agents have been verified before starting their data exchange. For that, the smart contract will define its software root of trust which is the first verifier to be used in the process. This verifier is defined arbitrarily as the agent of highest attestation freshness, meaning the last (positively) verified agent or at the very first agent verification a seed verifier, reputed trustworthy. The mutual attestation of the first of the two agents is produced by the other agent acting as verifier and fed with the reference measurement by the smart contract. At the end of this first attestation, the verified agent becomes the root of trust and serves as the verifier of the second agent.

The general workflow is given in the two figures below. Figure 20 shows the wrapping process of the agents, the store of the reference measures by the SECaaS and the agents enrollment on the blockchain.

Figure 21 shows the bidirectional mutual scheme using the root of trust (which is represented in grey).

FIGURE 20. AGENT REWRITING SEQUENCING

FIGURE 21. AGENT MUTUAL ATTESTATION SEQUENCING

4.3.7. Secure Execution Monitoring

MAS agents need to be hardened for higher resilience against various attacks and monitored to establish trust in a timely manner. To that end, we consider the initial set of measures made of proven evidence related to: i) the effectiveness of agents’ actual execution; ii) the validity of the authentication of the agent at its start-up phase; and iii) the agent last runtime integrity measurement check passed. Further healthy measurement can be considered typically through an accurate tracing of the software

control flow during execution, a method to infer any type of software attacks including vulnerability exploitation. This method can also be used to explicitly notify that the agent control flow does not deviate from the normal. A few changes on the agents' software need to be carried out.

These changes can either result from source level changes or be applied directly on the agent executable file, prior to deployment. Figure 21 shows how original agents are loaded into the binary hardening tool and transformed into protected variants (labelled (A)), which are both hardened against the confidentiality and integrity loss attempts and monitored by interfacing with the ledger. The global agent's integrity consists of checking that the agent has not been tampered by interception before being loaded, has not been tampered by local memory introspection during its execution, and that the agent is effectively running. The last criterion enables to infer denial of service attacks on the agent or on its platform by resource attrition. The monitoring delivers periodic integrity and activity status to an application running in the service orchestrator (labelled B in Figure 21).

4.4. Near Real-Time Secure MAS Operation

Using a DLT-based solution for inter-agent communication would add delay to the message exchange, which would prevent service operation near real-time. For this very reason, we propose combining DLT and extended VLANs (VXLAN) [3] to bring any added delay to a minimum; DLT exchange is kept offline, while VXLANs are used for near real-time communication among the agents (labelled C in Figure 21). VXLAN is a network encapsulation technology that allows creating an overlay over a physical network to provide a service abstraction layer in virtualized environments. This solution provides quick set up and enables creating millions of networks in parallel (simultaneous segments). At the same time, VXLAN presents some security concerns, such as the possibility for *rogue devices* to join one or more multicast groups and inject fake traffic. Encryption protocols, such as IPsec, encrypt both the content and the inner headers, which reduces rogue risk, as compared to other real-time encryption protocols at the application level.

In addition, to reduce the delay added for encryption and to allow other MAS agents to verify and trace communications, in our implementation we use pre-shared secrets. Then, such solution needs from an authentication infrastructure for authorized agents to obtain and distribute such secrets. We rely on DLT

for that purpose. In particular, the security intrinsic features of DLTs can be used to, once the association between agents is agreed, securely manage VXLANs as communication channels among the agents. Note that the impact of the consensus mechanism used is limited to the set-up phase of the dynamic associations between agents and does not have an impact on the actual exchanges between them once the associations are established.

4.5. MAS Deployment

The workflow proposed for ML Pipeline (including the agents in the MAS and their connectivity) deployment is sketched in Figure 22, which is carried out as a part of the deployment of the network service (NS). We assume that the MLFO has been previously configured with the needed credentials in the DLT network. The workflow consists of two phases: i) ML pipeline deployment; and ii) agents' configuration and secret/key exchange. The SMO initiates the workflow after the NS is deployed (0 in Figure 22).

FIGURE 22. ML PIPELINE DEPLOYMENT WORKFLOW

The SMO starts with the ML pipeline deployment and requests the definition of a ML pipeline for the NS and provides its details, including the location of the VNFs (1). Based on the NS details and the requirements of the ML pipeline in terms of delay and throughput among the agents, as well as the required IT resources of the agents, the MLFO requests the topology DB to compute a graph with the resources in the network infrastructure that meet the requirements and can be used to support the ML pipeline (2). With such data, the MLFO computes the optimal ML pipeline design and sends back a descriptor containing the location where the agents need to be deployed, the image to be installed and the connectivity to be created. A list of iterations is generated that includes the communication of SMO with the IMLs for the deployment of the agents encapsulated into containers (3), and with the SDN controller for managing the connectivity (4). Once the agents are running and the connectivity is available, the ML pipeline is deployed, and the configuration phase starts (5). When the MLFO receives the request to configure the agents, it sends the initial configuration that includes the addresses of the VNFs and that of the other agents, as well as the algorithms that every agent runs (6). After that, the MLFO compiles the smart contract that it will be used to store the secret/key for that ML pipeline (7). Next, the MLFO creates the DLT accounts for the agents, deploys the smart contract and register the addresses with credentials to interact with the smart contract (8). In this way, the MLFO can control the access to the smart contract and add or revoke permissions if needed in case of ML pipeline reconfiguration. Once the addresses are registered, the MLFO distributes the credentials to interact with the smart contract among the agents involved in the ML pipeline (9). The agents connect to the smart contract through the local DLT node. The MLFO generates a random key that uses to initialize IPsec for secure communication through the established VXLAN and pushes the key to the smart contract (10). At this time, the deployment of the NS ends from the viewpoint of SMO. Once the transaction is validated by the DLT network, agents receive a notification, download the key and use for secure communications with other entities in the ML pipeline (11) for near-real-time control of the NS.

5. Robust, sustainable and privacy preserving AI in DESIRE6G

Preliminary investigations are underway to study how intelligence can be integrated into the edge to address the demanding 6G requirements. Moreover, we also explored how the edge resources are effectively used for deriving EDGE intelligence. Finally, preliminary studies have been conducted to employ ML-based approaches to address problems on orchestration and lifecycle management of network services.

5.1. Distributed Edge Intelligence

FIGURE 23. FEDERATED SETTING FOR EDGE COMMUNICATION/COMPUTING

A federated setting (Figure 23) is sought as a platform for deploying the intended edge intelligence, where we propose a federated learning (FL) framework to handle the common model training deficiencies due to local dataset heterogeneity [9]. The agents are physical entities such as DESIRE6G edge sites, DESIRE6G UEs, who have their own computational resources, have access to their local datasets, and can communicate with a central entity referred to as the parameter server. Parameter server itself is again a physical entity. Parameter server is responsible for combining local machine learning models of the agents during the training phase to yield the global model. We note that the physical agents depicted in Figure 23 should not be confused with the agents discussed in Section 3 for services. It is worth noting that the privacy of the local datasets is intrinsically guaranteed within the realm of FL. The proposed framework is general in the sense that any supervised learning application

can be deployed while preserving the privacy of the local datasets of the agents, even if the datasets among the agents are heterogeneous.

For example, one may think of application specific or system specific machine learning tasks, where the SMO can play the role of the parameter server and DESIRE6G edge sites can play the role of agents. Medical health monitoring system is another application that relies on DESIRE6G architecture, where the SMO can play the role of the parameter server and DESIRE6G edge sites, one for each geographically distributed hospital premise, can play the role of agents. Of course, one can also imagine applications in which a DESIRE6G edge site plays the role of the parameter server while DESIRE6G UEs play the role of agents. Although FL provides a learning framework where multiple agents train a collaborative model while preserving the privacy of their local data, its state-of-the-art approaches, such as Federated Averaging (FedAVG), are known to perform poorly when the local data is non-identically distributed across participating agents [19]. This is due to that FedAVG and its variants solve the distributed learning problem by minimizing the empirical distribution of the local losses assuming that the datasets are drawn from the same distribution. They subsequently suffer from instability in convergence and fail to have a good Out-of-Distribution (OoD) generalization in unseen environments. In contrast, the proposed framework obviates the issues aforementioned, by reformulating the classic problem definition into an Invariant Risk Minimization (IRM) and by applying FL to the modified formulation. The solution method is carried out by introducing a representation learner that is trained to reveal the causal representations in the data samples, which in turn performs causal inference by optimizing the predictor on such representations. We jointly train the extractor and predictor functions across the training environments and show that their composition generalizes well in unseen environments. More technical details are documented in our paper [9].

Our preliminary experiments are conducted in a reflective intelligent surface (RIS) enabled wireless network. In this respect, RISs play the role of agents. It is worth pointing out that a RIS is a specialized structure that can be controlled (phase tuned) so that the propagation characteristics of electromagnetic waves between transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) are changed for improved wireless communication or sensing applications. Figure 24 depicts a concise setup considered in this respect. Roughly speaking, RIS can be optimized to change the channel between Tx and Rx. In a heterogeneous

multi-RIS setting, optimizing phases of RISs do not scale in a computationally feasible manner with classic optimization techniques due to the combinatorial nature of the problem [20].

In our experiment, we use the proposed framework to train a neural network to predict the phases of reflecting elements under heterogeneity. More specifically, we consider 3 environments with heterogeneous data. The environment 1 and 2 are used to train the neural networks. Environment 3 is not employed during the training process and thus considered to be OoD.

FIGURE 24. DEPLOYING INTELLIGENCE AT RIS

We plot the evolution of the test accuracy of proposed algorithm and the VANILA-FL, the baseline, see Figure 25. Within the heterogeneous environments in which the models are trained (i.e., environments 1 and 2), VANILA-FL and the proposed method perform similarly with an accuracy of 90%. When testing in a totally different environment (environment 3), the accuracy of VANILA-FL drops to 68%, highlighting its lack of robustness. However, the proposed algorithm maintains its accuracy at a level of 80% demonstrating its robustness for heterogeneity. This implies empirically that the proposed method does not overfit to the statistical correlations in the channels. Empirical results suggest that, unlike the state-of-the-art algorithms, the proposed distributed method is robust against heterogeneous environments.

FIGURE 25 CONVERGENCE OF ALGORITHMS

FIGURE 26. EDGE COMMUNICATION/COMPUTING FOR INTELLIGENCE

In addition to the FL framework, we also investigate a setting with multiple agents without a parameter server for coordination[10]. More specifically, we consider a setup involving multiple physical agents (See Figure 26) communicating with their neighbours to train a global machine learning model, without the

intervention of a superior agent. The goal is to achieve consensus on model parameters with fast convergence. Our proposed method combines proximal algorithms with second-order Newton Hessian approximations. We leverage edge communication to derive the intelligence, i.e., the ML model, that can be ultimately shared among the agents. The proposed algorithm is a distributed solution method where local solutions are coordinated with neighbouring agents to obtain the global solution. We refer the reader to our paper [10] for more technical details. The proposed algorithms are again general in the sense that any application specific or system specific machine learning tasks can be incorporated into the proposed setting. For instance, DESIRE6G edge sites or UEs can play the role of agents. More details on how the setting is deployed with the DESIRE6G architecture is to be further scrutinized.

Algorithm	Comp. Energy [J]	Comm. Energy [J]	Total Footprint [g-CO2-eq]
DGD	$5.97E-2$	$4.55E-4$	
DIN	$1.32E-2$	$0.82E-4$	
Newton Tracking	$2.69E-2$	$1.41E-4$	
Network Newton	$7.96E-2$	$1.83E-4$	

FIGURE 27. COMPUTATION/COMMUNICATION ENERGY COSTS AND CORRESPONDING CARBON FOOTPRINTS FOR THE PHISHING DATASET FOR A TARGET OPTIMALITY GAP 10^{-5}

We conduct numerical experiments to evaluate the performance of our proposed algorithm DIN, against first- and second-order algorithms, distributed gradient descent (DGD), Network Newton (NN) [21], and Newton Tracking (NT) [22], under different network topologies. Figure 27 reports the energy consumption and the carbon footprint required by the four algorithms to achieve a 10^{-5} optimality gap using the phishing dataset [23]. We observe that DGD's total energy consumption is the highest, and so is its carbon footprint. Although DGD is computationally less expensive, it requires a very large number of communication rounds to achieve the target optimality gap inducing high communication energy cost. On the other hand, Network Newton consumes the highest computation energy since Network Newton performs two matrix inversion operations in each communication round. Finally, DIN requires lower energy for both computation and communication due to its fast convergence while performing a single matrix inversion operation in each communication round.

This approach effectively utilizes edge resources, resulting in fast convergence and improved energy efficiency. Additionally, the method ensures privacy preservation as no local data is exposed during the training process. It is worth pointing out that the agents considered in the setup can be a set of base stations or any set of distributed agents who are seeking a global ML model through communications with neighbours.

5.2. Forecasting Element to support 6G operations

A novel Forecasting element (FE) is under study (currently being designed) to assist the automatic operations at the RAN. The FE runs at the edge nodes, consuming the near real time telemetry data collected from the network to produce forecasting metrics to assist in slice control (e.g., for service assurance). The adoption of forecasting metrics allows to implement near-real time operations with margin in time.

The FE will be derived from previous implementations , providing a lightweight a flexible solution. The definition of the APIs for both gathering the input data (input plugin) and exposing the forecasting metrics (output plugin) is ongoing, following the pervasive monitoring system design. The main task of the FE is to work with the Input features collected from the radio segment, encompassing the UEs telemetry data. Some preliminary activity is ongoing, collecting from a RIC some of the available metrics (i.e., the widebandCQI), by exploiting xApp implementation and existing APIs. Figure 28 shows a possible scenario of application of the proposed solution, exploiting the telemetry data collected form the near-real time RIC to perform the slice adaptation.

FIGURE 28. FE AND RADIO SEGMENT

More specifically, a specific forecasting job will be allocated in the FE for each slice. The job will run an ad-hoc defined forecasting model (i.e., Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM), Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), Convolutional Network). The FE will offer the possibility to automatically update the adopted algorithms, by performing the online training with the latest samples of the input features, adapting to the different scenarios.

The forecasting metrics will be then adopted to trigger the slice reconfiguration via the near-RT RIC. In the preliminary considerations, the slice reconfiguration will be performed by enforcing the resource block group (RBG) for the UEs belonging to the slice, adapting to the radio conditions/application demands with margin in time.

5.3. Confidentiality preserving data exchange with third party xApp

In the course of the project, we will investigate the design and implementation of a simple, yet highly efficient software-implemented homomorphic encryption solution applied to the radio segment. Considering previous research activities, conducted in the soft-failure detection in optical communication networks, the solution, designed for image processing and demonstrated in [9] and in [10] will be exploited. The basic idea leverages a class of machine learning algorithms, largely adopted as dimensionality reduction techniques, that share a particular property of being invariant to data

rotation axis. This feature can be then exploited to scramble the telemetry data in a fast and effective way, hiding key information present in the original content.

In fact, based on this invariance property, a preliminary activity has been applied to optical networks [11] showing that the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) algorithm is capable to achieve a very similar performance in soft-failure classification for a specific telemetry dataset from an optical communication system using the data in its original form and in a randomly scrambled version.

FIGURE 29 CONFIDENTIALITY PRESERVATION SOLUTION

The schema shown in Figure 29 has been defined to transmit telemetry data from an optical system to a Kafka-based monitoring system. By leveraging a preservation plugin, implemented in a Kafka Streams plugin in the Kafka brokers, the scaling and scrambling solution has been implemented, allowing the transmission of data to an “untrusted” third-party cloud computing resources for analysis, without revealing sensitive spatial geometry information contained in the data. This reduces security and confidentiality concerns that arise with the deployment of on-cloud processing solutions for network condition assessment and prognostics. During the DESIRE6G activities, the described preliminary solution will be exploited in the Radio segment, allowing the distribution of radio telemetry metrics to xApps, without disclosing key information.

5.4. ML-based assisted SLA Decomposition

A network slice may span different parts of the network (i.e., access, core, and transport network) and could be deployed across multiple operators/infrastructure providers. As a first step towards service instantiation, it is required to decompose the E2E SLA to partial service level objectives (SLOs) assigned to each of these network segments/administrative domains (referred to hereafter as domains). These partial SLOs can be effectively used to perform resource allocation. AI-assisted SLA decomposition is considered key to automating 6G complex business processes [14].

The SMO determines the SLA decomposition for the incoming service request. We assume that it has limited knowledge of the state of the infrastructure for the underlying domains at the moment that SLA decomposition is performed. In fact, the only data available is historical feedback on admission control from each of the domains (e.g., based on feedback from local IML, SDN-C), from prior service requests. We also assume that an SLA with stricter SLOs (e.g., lower delay, larger throughput) is less likely to get accepted, that leads to a partial order relation for the SLAs and a monotonic probability of accepting the service request [15].

Existing approaches for SLA decomposition mainly employ heuristics, considering state information periodically reported by the underlying domains [41]. Authors in [42] propose an E2E SLA decomposition system, using supervised machine learning algorithms. In previous work [16] we (i) formulated the decomposition problem as a function of the SLA acceptance probability under the constraints set by the E2E SLOs while we (ii) proposed a parameter-free risk model per domain to estimate these probabilities constructed by observing the response of domain controllers to previous requests. However, the estimation of a parameter-free risk model is non-linear, hence computationally intensive. Defining the risk model is the actual challenge; the creation of a parameter-free risk model, given the limited observability of the network state and the monotonicity constraints, is an offline, time-intensive process depending on its accuracy [15]. In [16] we introduce risk models based on deep NNs to support the SLA decomposition process. To this end, we propose methods that allow NN-based risk models to approximate monotonic functions without compromising their expressiveness.

As exemplified in Figure 30 the context of DESIRE6G for the RAN/transport/core network, with an SLA involving the maximum delay for the E2E service:

1. The behavior of each domain is modelled by introducing a NN-based risk model given its historical feedback on admission control.
2. The SMO uses the NN-based risk models obtained from step (1) and the optimization engine (i.e., part of the policy component) to decompose the E2E SLA into delay budgets per domain (e.g., RAN, transport, core), such that the probability of the requested E2E service to be accepted/supported by all domain is maximized.

FIGURE 30. SLA DECOMPOSITION

Specifically, we propose five (5) different methods that allow NN-based risk models to approximate monotonic functions and compare them against a vanilla NN that is used as baseline. These are described extensively in [16] where we employ a synthetic multi-domain dataset to demonstrate the efficiency of our approach. To solve the SLA decomposition optimization problem, we use the sequential least squares programming algorithm (SLSQP) optimizer.

Most of these models perform robustly even with small datasets. Furthermore, they are capable of learning from a more complex dataset, as well as inferring in a constant time, thus SLA decomposition improves accordingly, increasing the accuracy and scalability of the approach. Regarding the time required for model construction, it scales linearly with the number of samples. This makes them also appropriate for online-learning risk models in the DESIRE6G dynamic environment.

Indicatively, Figure 31 provides (l) the ground truth for a particular domain where the different colour in the contour plots show different levels of acceptance probabilities (i.e., dark red 0.01 to dark green 0.99)

(II) the sampled points of the training data, where the green dots represent accepted service requests while red dots depict rejected ones and (III) one of the learned risk models for 100 samples.

FIGURE 31 RISK MODEL EVALUATION

The following Figure 32 provides the E2E acceptance probability for the various types of NN-based risk models considering different sample sizes. The dashed line indicates the theoretical optimum. Apart from the proposed 5 NN-based risk models, we include the method introduced in [17], which imposes monotonicity by penalizing derivatives (DP) with respect to inputs. The vanilla (baseline) NN performs poorly for small sample sizes. The proposed methods [16] including the DP [17] outperform the vanilla NN across all sample sizes. However, as the sample size increases, the difference in performance becomes marginal.

FIGURE 32 AVG. E2E ACCEPTANCE PROBABILITY.

5.5. Elastic Scaling

In DESIRE6G, appropriate scaling mechanisms need to be put in place for performance assurance, specifically when traffic loads and the availability of computational resources are stochastic. Broadly speaking, elasticity is the ability to increase and shrink selected resources in a systematic and autonomous manner, to adapt to workload changes [24]. The goal is to avoid any degradation in service performance, while maximizing the utilization of the shared physical resources. To that end we have investigated the problem of scaling edge (computing) resources in the context of a Cellular Vehicular-to-Network (C-V2N) service, adhering to the MAS approach in DESIRE6G.

C-V2X technology was introduced by 3GPP to allow vehicles to communicate with other vehicles (vehicle-to-vehicle, V2V), road users (vehicle-to-pedestrian, V2P), roadside infrastructure (vehicle-to-infrastructure, V2I), and cloud/edge servers (vehicle-to-network, V2N). For the V2N system, we consider a road segment in the coverage area of a base-station as depicted in Figure 33. The base-station provides connectivity to smartphone users and connected and automated vehicles (CAVs) along the road. CAVs uses V2N-based applications such as remote driving, hazard warning etc. V2N traffic is forwarded and processed in the edge of the network to satisfy delay constraints. In the context of DESIRE6G, the respective (service) agent(s) may decide upon scaling edge resources (i.e., employing the DESIRE6G IML) to meet the VN2 service requirements for their respective workload. We have investigated the scaling problem considering (i) the V2N service is supported by edge computing resources collocated with the base station the vehicle is associated to [26], or in combination with the application task offloading problem across multiple edge servers distributed throughout a city's metropolitan area [27].

FIGURE 33. SCALING EDGE RESOURCES IN D6G.

Focusing on the former, we employ Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) for deciding on how to scale-up/down computational resources. The strength of RL approaches lies in their ability to reason under uncertainty and can adapt to changes at runtime, which maps well onto the stochastic V2N environment. RL has been investigated before for scaling computing resources; authors in [28] to [31] provide ML/RL-based auto-scaling techniques in the context of cloud resource management. ML has been also employed for scaling virtualized network functions ([32] to [37]). For instance, DDPG has been utilized to predict a threshold vector of CPU loads that eventually triggers scaling, but not the scaling actions per se [36]. Authors in [37] formulate the scaling of computing resources as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) and propose an RL approach based on Q-learning. However, to enable flexible scaling decisions that can support surges in network traffic, we need to go beyond approaches that employ a limited action space, as such solutions often scale CPU in increments of one. In consequence, this would lead to scalability problems due to the high dimensional discrete action space. Instead, we propose the use of a DRL approach with continuous action space, introducing a discretization method supporting diverse scaling actions.

Specifically, we formulate the decision problem on how to scale-up/down resources as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) and address it using Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG). We propose the use of DDPG for problems over discrete action space with explicit ordering nature, such as the problem at hand, to address scalability issues from the explosion of action space. We further propose a discretization method (termed as Deterministic Ordered Discretization) that can be applied to off-the-

shelf RL algorithms that learn in continuous action spaces to address discrete problems with ordering properties.

We evaluate our approaches using a real-world vehicular trace data set and compare it with other solutions proposed for the same problem [38] namely, an Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) predictor, a Q-Learning (RL) algorithm and a Proportional Integral (PI) controller that aims to keep the most loaded CPU below a threshold of 60%. Furthermore we compare against Advantage Actor Critic (A2C) for scaling resources [39], as it outperforms respective DRL methods (i.e., Deep Q-Network) in a variety of RL benchmarks [40]. Indicatively Figure 34 and Figure 35 depict the average number of CPUs and reward that each solution obtains over the testing trace. DDPG outperforms existing solutions, reducing (at minimum) the average number of active CPUs by 23% while increasing the long-term reward by 24%.

FIGURE 34. AVERAGED NUMBER OF CPUS

FIGURE 35. AVERAGED REWARD

6. Conclusion

In this document we capture the work done in the context of WP3 for the first 11 months. This work done in coordination with WP2 has set the ground for the following steps of implementation and showcasing. A significant portion of DESIRE6G's high level architecture basic blocks have been studied individually and collectively for their interconnection inside the architecture. All these works are converging to create DESIRE6G Intelligent and secure management, orchestration, and control platform.

The SMO, based on open source projects will be powered by a novel intent-based service decomposition management for faster e2e service activation. Service DLT-backed service federation will be progressed, breaking service vendor lock-in with new offerers.

A deep tech survey on network function containerization has been done to reach the best compromise in terms of security and performance in the context of 6G networks, leading the development of DESIRE6G hybrid containers technology.

The MAS definition, position in the architecture as well as its agent instantiation and orchestration have been intensely discussed and are now finalized. Agents security has also been discussed to confer an individual resilience leveraging executable rewriting and separately to create an inter-agent trust and secure transfer leveraging DLT. On this respect, DLT technology fits well with the agent distributed intelligence, fostering distributed security through agent authentication and key distribution.

Last, our work is paving the way for the AI/ML works inside DESIRE6G, notably to confer robust and privacy-preserving edge AI, fastly-converging low-energy AI for RIS and Federated Element in RAN, a novel homomorphic encryption based confidential telemetry data transfer to xAPPs, a novel SLA decomposition using neural network overcoming the lack of parameters and a deep reinforcement learning used for resource scaling in C-V2X ground basis.

With the results of this phase, both in terms of general design, solution specifications and interfaces, we can progress to the following phases efficiently and concertedly.

7. References

- [1] K. Antevski and C. Bernardos, "Federation in Dynamic Environments: Can blockchain Be the Solution?," IEEE Communication Magazine, 2022
- [2] K. Antevski and C. Bernardos, "Federation of 5G services using distributed ledger," Wiley Special Issue.
- [3] L. Velasco and e. al, "Securing Multi-Agent Systems for the Near-Time Control of 6G Services," in EUCNC 2023.
- [4] O. Aluko and A. Kolonin, "Proof of reputation: An alternative consensus mechanism for blockchain systems," in IJNSA, 2021.
- [5] N. Jiang and e. al, "Reputation-driven Dynamic Node Consensus and Reliability Sharding Model in IoT Blockchain," in Algorithms, 2022.
- [6] I.R. Jenkins, S.W.Smith, Distributed IoT Attestation via Blockchain.
- [7] S.F.J.Jørgensen Ankergård et al."Permanant: Publicly Verifiable Remote Attestation for Internet of Things Through Blockchain" 2021.
- [8] Y. Rekhter, S. Hares, y T. Li, «A Border Gateway Protocol 4 (BGP-4)», Internet Engineering Task Force, Request for Comments RFC 4271, ene. 2006. doi: [10.17487/RFC4271](https://doi.org/10.17487/RFC4271).
- [9] C. B. Chaaya, S. Samarakoon and M. Bennis, "Federated Learning Games for Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces via Causal Representations,". Globecom 2023 – IEEE Global Communications Conference, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.01306.
- [10] A. Ghalkha, C. Ben Issaid, A. Elgabli and M. Bennis, "DIN: A Decentralized Inexact Newton Algorithm for Consensus Optimization," ICC 2023 - IEEE International Conference on Communications, Rome, Italy, 2023, pp. 4391-4396.
- [11] . F. Silva, A. Pacini, A. Sgambelluri and L. Valcarenghi, "Learning Long- and Short-Term Temporal Patterns for ML-Driven Fault Management in Optical Communication Networks," in IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 2195-2206, Sept. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TNSM.2022.3146869.

- [12] M. F. Silva, A. Pacini, A. Sgambelluri, F. Paolucci and L. Valcarenghi, "Confidentiality-preserving Machine Learning Scheme to Detect Soft-failures in Optical Communication Networks," 2022 European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC), Basel, Switzerland, 2022, pp. 1-4.
- [13] M. F. Silva et al., "Confidentiality-preserving machine learning algorithms for soft-failure detection in optical communication networks," in *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 15, no. 8, pp. C212-C222, August 2023, doi: 10.1364/JOCN.481690.
- [14] Wang, J. Liu, J. Li, and N. Kato, "Artificial intelligence-assisted network slicing: Network assurance and service provisioning in 6g," *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 49–58, 2023.
- [15] De Vleeschauwer D, Papagianni C, Walid A. Decomposing SLAs for network slicing. *IEEE Communications Letters*. 2020 Oct 22;25(3):950-4
- [16] Hsu CS, De Vleeschauwer D, Papagianni C. SLA Decomposition for Network Slicing: A Deep Neural Network Approach. *IEEE Networking Letters*. 2023 Aug 30.
- [17] X. Liu, X. Han, N. Zhang, and Q. Liu, "Certified monotonic neural networks," *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 33, pp. 15 427–15 438, 2020
- [18] "Unified architecture for machine learning in 5G and future networks," ITU-T, 2019. <https://www.itu.int/hub/publication/t-fg-ml5g-2019/>
- [19] Y. Zhao, M. Li, L. Lai, N. Suda, D. Civin, V. Chandra. "Federated learning with non-iid data", 2018 Jun. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1806.00582>
- [20] Ö. Özdoğan, E. Björnson. Deep learning-based phase reconfiguration for intelligent reflecting surfaces. In 2020 54th Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers 2020 Nov 1 (pp. 707-711). IEEE.
- [21] A. Mokhtari, Q. Ling, and A. Ribeiro, "Network Newton distributed optimization methods," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 146–161, 2016.
- [22] J. Zhang, Q. Ling, and A. M.-C. So, "A Newton tracking algorithm with exact linear convergence for decentralized consensus optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Signal and Information Processing over Networks*, vol. 7, pp. 346–358, 2021.
- [23] C.-C. Chang and C.-J. Lin, "LIBSVM: A library for support vector machines," *ACM Trans. Intell. Syst. Technol.*, vol. 2, no. 3, 2011 May. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/1961189.1961199>

- [24] A. Medeiros, A. Neto, S. Sampaio, R. Pasquini, and J. Baliosian, "Enabling elasticity control functions for cloud-network slice-defined domains," in NOMS 2020-2020 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1-7.
- [25] 3GPP TS 23.28, "Architecture enhancements for V2X services (Release 16)," Tech. Rep., March 2019
- [26] Hsu CS, Martín-Pérez J, Papagianni C, Grosso P. V2N Service Scaling with Deep Reinforcement Learning. In NOMS 2023-2023 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium 2023 May 8 (pp. 1-5). IEEE
- [27] Hsu CS, Martín-Pérez J, De Vleeschauwer D, Kondepu K, Valcarenghi L, Li X, Papagianni C. A Deep RL Approach on Task Placement and Scaling of Edge Resources for Cellular Vehicle-to-Network Service Provisioning. arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.09832. 2023 May 16.
- [28] S. Verma and A. Bala, "Auto-scaling techniques for IoT-based cloud applications: a review," Cluster Computing, pp. 1-35, 2021.
- [29] K. Rzacca, P. Findeisen et al., "Autopilot: Workload autoscaling at google," in Proceedings of the Fifteenth European Conference on Computer Systems, ser. EuroSys '20. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2020.
- [30] L. Toka, G. Dobreff et al., "Machine learning-based scaling management for kubernetes edge clusters," IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 958-972, 2021.
- [31] C. Bitsakos, I. Konstantinou, and N. Koziris, "Derp: A deep reinforcement learning cloud system for elastic resource provisioning," in 2018 IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing Technology and Science (CloudCom), 2018, pp. 21-29.
- [32] T. Subramanya and R. Riggio, "Machine learning-driven scaling and placement of virtual network functions at the network edges," in Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft). IEEE, 2019, pp. 414-422.
- [33] S. Rahman, T. Ahmed et al., "Auto-scaling VNFs using machine learning to improve QoS and reduce cost," in International Conference on Communications (ICC). IEEE, 2018, pp. 1-6
- [34] Y. Garí, D. A. Monge et al., "Reinforcement learning-based application autoscaling in the cloud: A survey," Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence, vol. 102, p. 104288, 2021.
- [35] L. Cao, P. Sharma et al., "{ENVI}: elastic resource flexing for network function virtualization," in 9th USENIX Workshop on Hot Topics in Cloud Computing (HotCloud 17), 2017.
- [36] H. Chai, "Traffic-aware Threshold Adjustment for NFV Scaling using DDPG," arXiv:1811.08116, 2018.

- [37] P. Tang, F. Li et al., “Efficient Auto-Scaling Approach in the Telco Cloud Using Self-Learning Algorithm,” in 2015 IEEE Global Communications Conference, 2015, pp. 1–6.
- [38] De Vleeschauwer D. et al. 5Growth data-driven AI-based scaling. In 2021 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit) 2021 Jun 8 (pp. 383–388). IEEE.
- [39] W. Beks, “Network Slice Elasticity using Machine Learning [Master’s Thesis, VU-UvA],” <https://www.ubvu.vu.nl/pub/fulltext/scripties/2826690900.pdf>, 2021.
- [40] V. Mnih, A. P. Badia et al., “Asynchronous methods for deep reinforcement learning,” in International conference on machine learning, 2016, pp. 1928–1937.
- [41] R. Su, D. Zhang, R. Venkatesan, Z. Gong, C. Li, F. Ding, F. Jiang, and Z. Zhu, “Resource allocation for network slicing in 5g telecommunication networks: A survey of principles and models,” IEEE Network, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 172–179, 2019.
- [42] M. Iannelli, M. R. Rahman, N. Choi, and L. Wang, “Applying machine learning to end-to-end slice sla decomposition,” In 2020 6th IEEE Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft) 2020 Jun 29 (pp. 92–99). IEEE.
- [43] DESIRE6G Deliverable D2.1: “D2.1 Definition of Use Cases, Service Requirements and KPIs/KVIs”